

**CAREGIVERS' SELF-MEDICATION PRACTICES FOR PERCEIVED FEBRILE
ILLNESSES AMONG UNDER-FIVE CHILDREN IN CENTRAL RIVER REGION,
THE GAMBIA**

BY

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EBDOER)**

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DECLARATION

I hereby declare that this work is an original research project carried out by Haita Ndimballan in the Department of Epidemiology and Medical Statistics (EMS).

The contents of this research project have not been submitted to any authorities or institution for the award of any other degree or certificate.

HAITA NDIMBALLAN

CERTIFICATION

This work titled Caregivers' self-medication practices for perceived febrile illness among under-five children in Central River Region is an original research project by Haita Ndimballan carried out in the Department of Epidemiology and medical Statistics (EMS) under my supervision.

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DEDICATION

I dedicate this entire work to the Almighty Allah who made it possible for this dissertation to be completed. And to my lovely husband and son.

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ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

ABR	Antibiotic resistance
BHS	Basic Health Service
AMR	Antimicrobial Resistance
CCI	Common Childhood illnesses
CFR	Case Fatality Rate
CRR	Centra River Region
LGA	Local Government Area
LMIC	Low- and Middle-Income Countries
LRR	Lower River Region
MOH	Ministry of Health
NBE	North Bank East
NBW	North Bank West
OTC	Over-The-Counter drugs
PHC	Primary Health Care
RHD	Regional Health Directorate
URR	Upper River Region
URTI	Upper Respiratory Tract Infections
VHS	Village Health Service
WCR	West Coast Region
WR1	Western Region 1
WR2	Western Region 2
WSMI	World Self-Medication Industry
SM	Self-Medication

ABSTRACT

Self-medication is the process of taking drugs, herbs, or home remedies on one's own initiative, or on the advice of another person, without consulting a healthcare professional. Drug use for under-five children by their caregivers without professional advice is a major concern worldwide and has drawn a lot of attention due to its potential to cause drug-drug interactions, overdose, and antimicrobial resistance. In the Gambia, there are only a handful of programs that control self-medication despite its harmful effects on children. Self-medication of under-five children has been reported in urban areas of the Gambia, however, studies on self-medication in rural areas are scarce in the literature. Therefore, this study assessed the knowledge, practices, and reasons for the self-medication of under-five children for perceived febrile illnesses by their caregivers in Central River Region, the Gambia.

This cross-sectional study was conducted between September and October 2023 among caregivers of under-five children from Central River Region, The Gambia. A mixed method was used to collect data. A survey was conducted among 406 caregivers using a semi-structured questionnaire. Knowledge of childhood febrile illnesses was assessed using 9-item questions. Focus group discussions and In-depth interviews were conducted using guides. Data were summarized using frequencies and percentages. Chi-square was used to test the association between socio-demographic characteristics and self-medication practice. Binary logistic regression was used to determine the predictors of self-medication. Level of significance was set at 5%. Atlas.Ti was used to analyse the qualitative part of the study.

The mean age (SD) of the caregivers was 31.1 ± 9.6 years and most 330(81.3%) were females. The prevalence of self-medication was 87(21.43%) and 165(40.6%) of the caregivers had good knowledge of childhood febrile illnesses. Caregivers within the age category 25-34 were less likely to practice self-medication than those younger (aOR=0.394; P=0.017). The odds of self-medication was higher among children who are ≥ 3 years old than those who are younger (aOR=9.435; p=<0.001). Respondents who received information from Friends on childhood febrile illnesses were more likely to self-medicate than those who did not (aOR=2.564; P=0.002). Respondents who got advice from neighbours (aOR=7.008; P=0.011) and pharmacists (aOR=4.746; P=0.039) were more likely to self-medicate their under-five children. Long waiting hours, lack of drugs at health facility, and past experience with self-medication, were the reasons promoting self-medication of under-five children.

The prevalence of self-medication is low, which may be explained by the poor knowledge of more than half of the caregivers on childhood febrile illnesses. The younger the age of a caregiver, the more likely the practice of self-medication in an under-five child. The identified predictors should be considered while designing policies on self-medication for febrile illnesses among under-five children in the Gambia.

Keywords: Caregivers, Self-medication practices, Under-five children, Central River Region, The Gambia.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Self-medication is the process of using drugs intending to treat self-recognized or medically diagnosed illnesses without advice or prescription from a health professional (Tsifiregna et al., 2016). Common illnesses for which children are often self-medicated include diarrhoea, fever, cough, and acute upper respiratory tract infections (URTI) (Edessa, Assefa, Dessie, Asefa, Dinsa, and Oljira, 2022). Self-medication is a global problem, especially among caregivers of under-five children (Simon and Kazaura, 2020) and it is more prevalent in developing countries (Mahmood et al., 2020). Many countries around the world have policies regarding self-medication. Some of these policies frown at self-medication, particularly, among vulnerable populations including under-five children. Studies have revealed that differences exist in the pattern of self-medication within one population and are influenced by numerous sociocultural factors among which socioeconomic status and education are often reported. The morbidity and mortality associated with self-medication for under-five children might make the achievement of theme 3 of the Sustainable Development Goals unrealizable if countries failed to either alleviate or eradicate self-medication. Self-medication is highly prevalent in developing countries, with Africa carrying the greatest burden (30-85%) (Ekambi et al., 2019).

The main issues with self-medication are resource wastage, an increase in disease resistance to medications, and major health risks such as unpleasant reactions and protracted suffering. Antimicrobial resistance is an issue that exists today everywhere, especially in underdeveloped nations where drugs are freely available. Therefore, the government needs to act to control appropriate self-medication. This can be accomplished by providing safe medications, coupled with appropriate usage instructions and, if necessary, medical advice (Bennadi, 2014). Self-medication only offers partial treatment, thereby masking other diseases and resulting in multi-drug resistance. This phenomenon leads to high morbidity and mortality (Cruz et al., 2022). More and more governments are promoting self-care for minor ailments, including self-medication. While appropriate self-medication can save treatment costs, it also saves travel and doctor's time, or consultation time. Information on self-medication is frequently sourced via friends, family, neighbours, chemists, previously

prescribed prescriptions, and advertisements in popular publications or newspapers. Currently, self-medication needs to be understood as the inclination and capacity of individuals/patients to assume an intelligent, autonomous, and knowledgeable role, not only concerning decision-making but also in the administration of those prophylactic, diagnostic, and remedial tasks which affect them (Bennadi, 2014). Antibiotics are widely used in young children around the world. This is most likely due to their vulnerability to infections, specifically upper respiratory tract infections (URTI) (Yu, Zhao, Stålsby Lundborg, Zhu, Zhao, and Xu, 2014). This raises great concerns about antibiotic abuse and antimicrobial resistance, especially among children (Olmeda et al., 2023). Over-the-counter (OTC) painkillers such as ibuprofen, aspirin, and paracetamol are used worldwide. These medications are mostly used to relieve minor pains, headaches, and menstrual cramps. If used as directed, painkillers are not harmful but can result in gastrointestinal infections and high blood pressure when abused. Due to their ease of access and lower costs, OTC drugs mainly serve as the first treatment option for many people. They are usually obtained from small-scale vendors, family members, and friends, without professional advice (Kawuma et al., 2021).

The World Health Organisation has noted that self-medication is now universally acknowledged to have a significant role in the healthcare system. This viewpoint has been influenced by the realisation that people have a responsibility for their own health and that seeking medical attention for minor illnesses is frequently needless. In many nations, advancements in people's general awareness, educational attainment, and socioeconomic standing provide a solid foundation for effective self-medication.

This study aimed to assess the knowledge, practices, and reasons for the self-medication of under-five children for perceived febrile illnesses by their caregivers in Central River Region, the Gambia.

1.2 Problem Statement

Self-medication remains a public health problem of important concern globally, with low-income countries bearing the huge burden of self-medication. In many advanced countries, procurement of essential drugs at the pharmaceutical store is only possible with a medical prescription, this is not usually the case in low-income countries. Most drugs used by children are taken either with or without a prescription outside of medical settings. Self-medication has been found to be the family's first line of defence against many illnesses in children (Eldalo, Yousif, and El-Hadiyah, 2013). Self-medication poses a global threat to lives, particularly in children. Drug use for under-five children by their caregivers is a major concern worldwide and has drawn a lot of attention. Numerous studies in this area have been carried out in both developed and developing nations, and they have all revealed a variety of issues, including prescription drug abuse and misuse as well as medication errors (Ouedraogo AS, Jean Pierre H, Bañuls AL, Ouédraogo R, and Godreuil S, 2017; Horumpende PG, Said SH, and Mazuguni FS, 2018; Kamati M, Godman B, and Kibuule D, 2019; Torres NF, Solomon VP, and Middleton LE, 2019).

Self-medication can lead to antimicrobial resistance if abused (Edessa et al., 2022). Globally, the prevalence of parental self-medication for children has been reported to be between 7 and 70% (Yuan, Du, Li, Deng, and Ma, 2022). Studies conducted in Madagascar, India, Greece, and Australia have reported prevalence rates of paediatric self-medication to be between 32 and 98% (Ukwishaka, Umuhoza, Cartledge, and McCall, 2020). Self-medication has been reported in The Gambia among students at an international university where the practice was very common (Oriavwote and Ikwuka, 2022). A similar study reported that 19% of women living in Farafenni, the Gambia and diagnosed with Malaria preferred to treat their symptoms at home instead of seeking professional treatment (Virginia Wiseman, Anthony Scott, Lesong Conteh, Brendan McElroy, and Warren Stevens, 2008). A cross-sectional study conducted among caregivers in urban areas of the Gambia whose under-five children were receiving malaria treatment at home showed a prevalence of self-medication less than 10% (Clarke, Rowley, Bøgh, Walraven, and Lindsay, 2003).

In the Gambia, the death rate per 1,000 is 8, the infant mortality rate is 31 per 1000 live births, and the life expectancy of 62 years for the total population. These high demographic indices in The Gambia are due to many lapses in the health system, poverty, and lack of political will on the part of leaders. It is also not impossible that self-medication contributed

to these poor health indicators in the country. Recently, more than 80 under-five children were hospitalized as a result of drug-induced Acute Kidney Injury (AKI), with a case-fatality rate (CFR) of 90% on account of self-medication (Bastani, Jammeh, Lamar, Malenfant, Adewuyi, Cavanaugh, Calloway, Crisp, Fofana, Christy Hallett, Jallow, Muoneke, Nyassi, Thomas, Troeschel, Yard, Yeh, and Bittaye, 2023).

1.3 Justification for the study

Enhancing the availability of healthcare for susceptible groups is undoubtedly a strategy to reduce poverty in emerging nations. Even after numerous political pledges such as Alma Ata (1978), the Bamako Initiative (1987), and the Millennium Development Goals (2000), the impoverished continue to face barriers to receiving high-quality healthcare (Kone, Lalou, Audibert, Lafarge, Dos Santos, Ndonky, and Le Hesran, 2015).

Self-medication is highly practiced in developing and underdeveloped countries. It encompasses both modern and traditional methods of treatment with no professional advice. Self-medication has been reported in studies conducted in Nigeria and Ghana where parents used home remedies and non-prescribed drugs (75%), respectively as the first option for managing childhood illnesses (Ahmed, Ijaz, Manzoor, and Sajjad, 2021). Evidence on self-medication has been gathered for various demographics and in several sub-Saharan African countries. However, few research have examined parents self-medicating their under-five children especially when it comes to antibiotic self-medication (Simon and Kazaura 2020). The practice of self-medication for under-five children in Sub-Saharan Africa is not well-documented in the literature (Ukwishaka et al., 2020). A study conducted among caregivers of under-five children in urban areas of the Gambia found that about 60% of women used paracetamol to self-medicate their children against malaria, while 16% used herbal remedies (Clarke et al., 2003) to achieve the same goals. However, studies on self-medication in rural areas of the Gambia are scarce in the literature.

1.4 Research questions

1. What is the knowledge of caregivers of under-five children on signs/symptoms of childhood illnesses?
2. What are the self-medication practices of caregivers of under-five children in Central River Region, the Gambia?
3. What are the factors influencing self-medication practices for perceived febrile illnesses in Central River Region, the Gambia?
4. What are the reasons for the self-medication of under-five children by caregivers in Central River Region, the Gambia?

1.5 Objectives

1.5.1 Broad Objective

The general objective of this study is to assess the caregivers' self-medication practices for perceived febrile illnesses among under-five children in the Central River Region, the Gambia.

1.5.2 Specific Objectives:

The specific objectives of the study are to:

1. Assess the knowledge of caregivers of under-five children on signs/symptoms of childhood illnesses in the Central River Region, the Gambia
2. Determine Self-medication practices for perceived febrile illnesses among caregivers of under-five children in the Central River Region, the Gambia.
3. Identify the factors influencing self-medication practices for perceived febrile illnesses in the Central River Region, the Gambia.
4. Explore in-depth reasons for self-medication of under-five children for perceived febrile illnesses in the Central River Region, the Gambia.

Operational definition of terms

For the purpose of the study, the following key terms were used in simple terms in order to make the participants understand the questions better.

Caregivers of under-five children

Caregivers were either the biological parents of the under-five children or any other person who took care of them four weeks before the study.

Self-medication

Self-medication has traditionally been defined as “the taking of drugs, herbs, or home remedies on one's own initiative, or on the advice of another person, without consulting a doctor” (Bennadi, 2014).

Febrile illness

It is the increase in body temperature in response to infectious diseases caused by bacteria, viruses, parasites, or fungal infections.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Overview and historical perspective of Self-Medication

Self-medication (SM) is an increasingly common and widespread practise worldwide. Due to antibiotic resistance, increased morbidity, drug-drug interactions, risk of adverse drug responses, and disease masking, it poses a public health danger. Though the term "self-care" has no universally accepted definition, it can be interpreted as a self-care practise that served as the first health care system and was inherited by subsequent generations. There have been discoveries of informational compilations regarding the ancient world's use of various plants and substances to treat a range of ailments (Baracaldo-Santamaría, Trujillo-Moreno, Pérez-Acosta, Feliciano-Alfonso, Calderon-Ospina, and Soler, 2022). Papyri dating back to 2000 BC in Egypt included over 900 distinct plant and mineral combinations as remedies for a range of ailments (Leake CD, 1965). Through self-care for our health, we engage in self-medication daily. Self-medication and self-care were seen as superfluous and possibly harmful practices in the West around the 1960s. Beginning in the early 1980s, medications that were previously only available with a prescription were made available without one, signalling the beginning of a new era in patient access to contemporary, efficacious treatments. Ibuprofen, which was prescribed for pain management, was one of the first products to be made available without a prescription in the US (1984) and the UK (1983). In 1986, hydrocortisone was made non-prescription available in Canada.

During the Fifth General Assembly in October 1979 in Australia, the World Self-medication Industry (WSMI) Board of Directors formally adopted and released a statement of WSMI Policy on Consumer Information and the Role of Labelling. "To provide all information necessary to enable an individual without medical training to use the medicine appropriately" is the policy's highlighted purpose for labelling (Global Self-Care Federation, 2010). In the 1990's, there was an increasing recognition in many parts of the world that people were managing or treating a large proportion of their ailments without always consulting a health professional. Health care in many nations is still characterized by this paternalistic attitude to medicine, which is reinforced by institutions built to cure illness rather than prevent it (Bennadi, 2014).

Children are more prone to a wide variety of illnesses and infections, particularly viral and bacterial ones, because of the fragile state of their immune systems. More than 80% of these

infections are viral and share many clinical signs and symptoms with bacterial infections. Self-medication is a serious health problem that can lead to several issues for children, including drug toxicity, antibiotic-induced drug resistance, increased drug use per person, and non-desired treatment. Studies have revealed that 3% of congenital anomalies are caused by self-medication with antibiotics. It has been noted that many patients' families or the pharmacy choose whether to give them antibiotics (Nazari, Chezani-Sharahi, Eshrati, Yadegari, Naghshbandi, Movahedi, and Moradzadeh, 2022).

The risks of self-medication include not having a clinical evaluation of the disease performed by a healthcare professional, which could lead to a wrong diagnosis and prescription selection, delays in obtaining the right therapy, using too much or too little medication, and using it for an extended period of time. Hazardous drug interactions, the emergence of hazardous drug reactions, and the concealment of a serious illness are other possible hazards.

The possibility of germs becoming resistant to medicines used for self-medication is another issue (Chipwaza, Mugasa, Mayumana, Amuri, Makungu, and Gwakisa, 2014). Self-medication practices vary among households and might encompass both conventional and contemporary forms (Okunola, 2020). The increasing prevalence of inappropriate self-medication has been linked to several factors, including the accessibility of over-the-counter (OTC) medications, the need for self-care, the absence of functional health care services, poverty, ignorance, the prevalence of drug advertising, the high cost of attending healthcare facilities, the availability of drugs outside of pharmacies, and insufficient family support (Salami and Adesanwo, 2015). Self-medication using over-the-counter medications, such as analgesics, is prevalent in Sub-Saharan Africa. In Nigeria, people of all paediatric age groups, both in rural and urban areas, frequently self-medicate for fevers and other symptoms.

2.2 Prevalence of self-medication among caregivers of under-five children

Self-medication is a usual practice among caregivers of children (Tsifiregna et al., 2016). The global prevalence of parental self-medication in children has been reported to be between 7 and 70% (Yuan et al., 2022). A systematic review and meta-analysis conducted in Low- and middle-income countries (LMIC) showed that the prevalence of self-medication was between 50 and 93.8% which yielded a pooled estimate of 78% (Edessa et al., 2022). This is similar to a cross-sectional study conducted in Borama district, Somaliland, which revealed that 82% of the caregivers were found to be practicing self-medication. These findings are consistently higher than those reported in several East African studies including Kenya, Uganda, and

Ethiopia, where the prevalence of self-medication was 53.5%, 75.7%, and 50% respectively (Hareed, 2018). Similar studies conducted in Cameroon and Nairobi also reported self-medication of under-five children with prevalences between 50 and 60% (Ekambi et al., 2019; Kamati et al., 2019). These findings are lower than the findings made by (Simon B and Kazaura, 2020) in their cross-sectional study among 612 parents/caregivers in Tanzania whose under-five children got sick at least once during the twelve months prior to the study. The prevalence of self-medication to the children with antibiotics was 78.6%. this finding is in conformity with that of a cross-sectional study by (Ukwishaka et al., 2020) conducted among caregivers of children in Rwanda, where the practice of self-medication was 78% which include the use of both modern and traditional medicines.

Self-medication in children under five have been previously reported in Nigerian and Sudan where the prevalence was 99.4% and 95.7% respectively. These are higher than the findings of Babalola, who reported that 33.5% of the mothers in Kaduna who thought about treating their feverish children right away self-medicated at home (Babalola, Ajumobi, and Ajayi, 2020). Similar findings were made by (Omale, Oka, and Okeke, 2021) in a recent household survey conducted in the Nigerian state of Ebonyi, where they found that most (70%) caregivers of children in rural communities had sought treatment from drugstores, medicine vendors, or traditional healers without first undergoing diagnostic tests. In a Gambian study conducted by (Oriavwote and Ikwuka, 2022) among university students reported that the prevalence of self-medication was 38.9%. Our environment encourages self-medication because over-the-counter drugs are easily accessible and drug hawkers are common. Although self-medication may be encouraged in the case of a few minor illnesses to avoid overcrowding clinics and overworking limited practitioners, self-medication has serious consequences.(Abiodun and Ayinboumwan, 2022).

2.3 Caregivers' knowledge of childhood febrile illnesses

In developing countries, most neonatal deaths occur at home. Many of these deaths are the result of parents failing to recognize the signs of a serious illness and delaying the decision to seek medical attention. A study conducted in Riyadh City, Saudi Arabia among mothers and caregivers revealed that their knowledge of signs/symptoms of childhood illnesses was low, with only 37% of them being able to identify at least three danger signs of disease (Abu-Shaheen, Alfayyad, Riaz, Nofal, Almatary, Khan, and Heena, 2019). A case-control study conducted in Bogota, Columbia by Cruz et al. 2022 among parents/caregivers of under-fives who self-medicated their children revealed that 29% of the cases think that antibiotics are a

good way to treat a cold, compared to 22% in the control group. Additionally, compared to 50% of controls, 66% of caregivers who self-medicated thought that antibiotics shortened the duration of viral infections. Of the cases, 45% think antibiotic therapy can be stopped as soon as the fever goes down (Cruz et al., 2022). Simon and Kazaura in cross-sectional study in Bagamoyo district, Tanzania to determine the prevalence and factors responsible for the self-medication of under-five children by their parents/caregivers. In their findings, the knowledge of caregivers on antibiotic use for their under-five children was very low (Simon and Kazaura, 2020).

A study conducted by (Okunola, Aluko, and Aroke, 2023) in Southwestern Nigeria assessed the knowledge of caregivers of under-five children on common childhood illnesses (CCI). The respondents were able to list measles, mumps, respiratory tract infections, malaria, otitis media (ear infection), gastroenteritis (diarrhoea and vomiting), and febrile convulsion as common paediatric ailments. The carers demonstrated an excellent broad understanding of the CCI that was given to them. They properly recognised the disorders linked to the symptoms. It is a strongly held belief that a caregiver's level of expertise or knowledge will influence the standard of care they provide for their children under-five.

2.4 Self-medication practices among caregivers of under-five children

The practice of self-medication has been in existence from time immemorial. It is of human nature to perceive the existence of an illness through pain or apparent signs. Self-medication is usually practiced for both minor and chronic illness especially if those involved in it are with the conviction that they possess good knowledge of illness. In an attempt to treat perceived illnesses, many people result to self-medication for various reasons instead of seeking professional advice (Baracaldo-Santamaría et al., 2022). Around the world, the usage of complementary and alternative medicine which includes home cures, handcrafted pharmaceuticals, and most importantly herbal products is steadily rising. In many places, it even serves as the primary mode of treatment. Although it is typically thought of as a safe or natural approach to treating illnesses, pharmacology finds it extremely relevant because some herbal medications can combine with conventional medicine to produce dangerous side effects, such as hepatotoxic consequences (Singh J, Gautam C, and Singh R, 2012).

2.4.1 Common Sources of medication

Medications are mostly obtained from either health facilities or drug stores. Drug hawkers are also suppliers of medications although their activities are illegal and hence conducted clandestinely. A study conducted in Tanzania by (Simon and Kazaura, 2020) found that most of the caregivers purchased drugs from drugstores. A Nigerian study conducted in rural areas of Ebonyi state revealed that most of the caregivers of under-five children studied sought medications from drugstores, medicine vendors, or traditional healers. The most common sources of medications found among students practicing self-medication in an international university in the Gambia were drug store, friends, family members, leftover drugs and home remedies (Oriavwote and Ikwuka, 2022).

2.4.2 Most commonly used drugs/medicines for self-medication

Medications commonly used by caregivers to treat their under-five children include both modern and traditional remedies. In developing countries, among the most commonly used medications are analgesics and antipyretics (44.3%), followed by nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory medicines (36.4%), and antihistamines (8.5%) (Paudel S and Aryal B, 2020). Several studies in Sub-Saharan Africa have shown variations in caregivers' medication preferences such as the use of amoxicillin when it comes to self-medicating their children (Kibuule, Kagoya, and Godman 2016; Nepal and Bhatta, 2018; Orumpende , Said, and Mazuguni, 2018; Ateshim, Bereket, and Major, 2019).

Self-medication of under-five children using antibiotics has been reported by (Simon B and Kazaura M, 2020) in their study conducted among caregivers of under-five children in Bagamoyo district, Tanzania. Amoxicillin was the most used antibiotic by the caregivers to treat their children followed by cotrimazole and ampicillin/cloxacillin. Paracetamol has been reported in a study as the first line of treatment for most caregivers of under-five children before seeking professional care (Okunola, 2020). This is in conformity with a study conducted among university students in the Gambia where paracetamol was used by almost half of the participants to treat minor ailments (Oriavwote and Ikwuka, 2022). Another Gambian study showed that 60% of caregivers of under-five children used modern medicines to treat malaria while 16 % used herbal remedies.

2.4.3 Common childhood conditions for which self-medication is practiced

There is a wide range of illnesses or conditions of children which prompt caregivers to self-medicate them. A study conducted in Brazil among caregivers of under-five children revealed that the conditions for which self-medication was highly practiced include fever, cold and pain (Pons, Pizzol, Knauth, and Mengue, 2023). This is similar to a study conducted in Islamabad, Pakistan, which found that the most likely symptoms to be self-medicated by caregivers of under-five children were pain, respiratory diseases, gastrointestinal diseases, allergies and sleeping disturbances (Aqeel, Shabbir, Basharat, Bukhari, Mobin, Shahid, and Waqar, 2014). These symptoms o

2.4.4 Common sources of self-medication information

There are numerous ways in which people seek for advice before deciding to self-medicate. A study conducted in Delhi, India, reported that caregivers of under-five children often seek information on childhood illness from online sources, family members, neighbours, health care providers, both professional and unprofessional, and pharmacists (Pons et al., 2023) . This is supported by a Gambian study conducted by (Oriavwote and Ikwuka, 2022) which found that the most common source of self-medication information for the participants was online sources. These practices may be explained by the fast-growing technology and the seemingly “reduced number of hours a day” which makes people choose cheaper and faster ways of treating their conditions without having to spend time and resources at health facilities.

2.5 Factors influencing caregivers' Self-medication practices

There are numerous factors that prompt people to resort to self-medication rather than seeking for appropriate treatment options. These range from sociodemographic, socio-economic, and socio-cultural factors that influence the attitude and behaviours of people.

2.5.1 Age of a child

The practice of self-medication of under-five children in some cases has been found to be influenced by the age of the child. According to the literature now available, children under the age of five are more likely to receive antibiotics than other drugs because they are more vulnerable to common respiratory, urinary tract, and diarrheal illnesses than children in other age groups (Simon and Kazaura, 2020). This can be influenced by the fact that children under the age of five have weaker immune systems compared to older children and can die faster or develop serious complications if their illnesses are left untreated or if treatment is delayed. Therefore, caregivers of under-five children do not waste any time in trying to treat these illnesses to prevent worsening situations.

2.5.2 Age of a caregiver

Socio-demographic factors including the age of a caregiver can influence the practice of self-medication of under-five children. A study conducted by (Simon and Kazaura , 2020) among caregivers of under-five children, found that age of the caregiver was significantly associated with self-medication practice, with a unit decrease in the age of the caregiver resulting to a higher practice of self-medication. This phenomenon explains the reason why younger mothers or caregivers are more engaged into risky health seeking behaviours than older mothers or caregivers. It might be due to their little experience with regards to childcare and unwillingness to visit health facilities when needed. Contrary to this is the study by (Ukwishaka et al., 2020) among caregivers of under-five children in Rwanda, who found that an increase in the age of a caregiver increases the likelihood of self-medication.

2.5.3 Place of Residence

Several studies have also found self-medication to be closely associated with the type of residence. A study conducted among urban and rural settlements of Islamabad reported that self-medication was higher among residents in urban areas and higher among literates (Aqeel et al., 2014). This is contrary to the findings made by (Sougou, 2017) among under-five children in Senegal, who found that self-medication was very common among caregivers in rural areas.

2.5.4 Wealth Index

Enhancing the availability of health care for marginalised groups is undoubtedly a strategy for mitigating poverty in developing nations. Despite numerous political pledges [Alma Ata (1978)¹, the Bamako Initiative (1987), the Millennium Development Goals], the impoverished continue to face barriers to receiving high-quality healthcare. In West Africa, the annual number of outpatient consultations per person is less than 0.6, despite the World Health Organization's recommendation of one consultation per year. Nonetheless, health demands have grown more urgent due to shifting lifestyles and rising rates of school enrolment. The disparities in access to healthcare are becoming less acceptable by people (Kone et al., 2015).

Poverty is one of the major public health problems devastating many lives by limiting numerous opportunities for those affected. Literature has shown that poor wealth index is significantly associated with the practice of self-medication. A study conducted in Dakar, Senegal by (Kone et al., 2015) to assess the impact of neighbourhood on the use of health care among febrile children from urban poor household showed that the poorest households in Dakar have a high prevalence of self-medication. Nonetheless, the impoverished who live in affluent neighbourhoods with good amenities typically act like their affluent neighbours. They seize the chances the place presents and modify their actions accordingly. It's a therapy option that is frequently the only one available to the poorest.

This is similar to a study by (Simon B and Kazaura M, 2020) in Bagamoyo District Council, Tanzania where self-medication of children was significantly associated with household income and low knowledge about medications. However, it was found that parents/caregivers of under-five children who had high incomes were more likely to seek health care from a health facility. Neighbourhood resources (facilities and social networks) will enhance health care among the poorest and lessen access inequities, even though household socioeconomic

features have a significant influence on children's health care. When the community offers resources, it could be able to assist in getting over the financial obstacle without being a major component.

2.5.5 Level of Education

Over the years, educational level of a caregiver has been identified as one of the predictors of self-medication practice of under-five children. Evidence from a study conducted by (Cruz et al., 2022) reported that there was reduced self-medication practiced with an increasing level of education. Similar findings have been reported from China and Mozambique where a significant association was found between an increase in the level of education and reduced self-medication practice.

2.5.6 Health system factors

Throughout the world, self-medication is a common practice frequently influenced by lapses in the healthcare systems. This ranges from ineffectiveness of services, inadequate health insurance schemes for the less privileged and lack of political will to address such challenges. The primary causes of self-medication in many sub-Saharan African nations are problems with the health system, such as a shortage of trained staff, inadequate diagnostic capacity, and unlicensed and unqualified medical personnel who prescribe medications to patients with no apparent medical conditions (Zainab Ismail, Anmol Mohan, Christophe Ngendahayo, Abdullahi Tunde Aborode, Abid, Ana Carla dos Santos Costa, Shoaib Ahmad, and Essar, 2021).

2.5.7 Perceived behavioural control

The theory of planned behaviour describes how Patients' perceptions of their own suffering and unique coping mechanisms, in addition to their attitudes towards medications, are significant factors in their decision to self-medicate (Pineles and Parente, 2013). Self-medication is reported in a study by (Ukwishaka et al., 2020) conducted in Rwanda among parents/caregivers of under-five children. These include parents/caregivers having the conviction that a child's illness is not serious and does not require professional medical attention, the beliefs of parents/caregivers that they are knowledgeable about symptoms of childhood disease based on their past experiences of self-medicating their ill children.

A study conducted among parents/caregivers of under-five children in Bagamoyo district, Tanzania reported that about a quarter of the participants confirmed that they have been self-

medicating their children of similar illnesses in the past without deeming it necessary to seek professional medical attention. Of the 730 parents/caregivers, 207 had the belief that it is quite normal to self-medicate a child before considering going to any health facility (Simon B and Kazaura, 2020). Similar to this are the findings made by (Muoneke, Una, and Mbachu, 2018) in which caregivers who self-medicated their under-five children believed that they possess good knowledge of the illness based on past experiences with the same illnesses. Among his findings were long waiting hours at health facilities, and beliefs that an illness is too trivial to warrant professional medical attention.

2.6 Self-medication and Anti-microbial resistance / Antibiotic resistance

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) has emerged as a concern in the modern world, with estimates that by 2050 it will be responsible for 10 million annual deaths. The widespread and inappropriate use of antibiotics in the form of non-prescription and leftover access is a prevalent cause of the global rise in resistance to these medications (Edessa et al., 2022). According to a recent scoping review, 62% of antibiotic use in communities worldwide, occurs without a prescription (Auta, Hadi, Oga, Adewuyi, Abdu-Aguye, Adeloje, Strickland-Hodge, and Morgan, 2019).

Antimicrobial medicine consumption in China is half of the world's total, and the country reports significant rates of antimicrobial resistance, particularly in children (Lin, Harbarth, Wang, and Zhou, 2020). Other similar research found that the pooled estimate for the use of non-prescribed antibiotics was 66% in high-income nations (Grigoryan L, Germanos G, Zoorob R, Juneja S, Raphael JL, Paasche Orlow MK, and Trautner BW, 2019) and 69% in low-income nations (Belachew SA, Hall L, and Selvey LA, 2021). Due to the high occurrence of diseases in LMICs, extensive usage of non-prescribed antibiotics puts the environment at a higher risk of acquiring antibiotic resistance (ABR) than any other environment (Edessa et al., 2022).

2.7 Conceptual Framework

Figure 2.1: A conceptual framework showing the relationship between self-medication (dependent variable) and its predictors (independent variable)

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

3.1.1 Study Area

The Gambia, located in West Africa, is the smallest country in mainland Africa. It stretches about 48 Km from the Atlantic Ocean. The country is a narrow strip of land on either side of the river Gambia and occupies an area of 11,295 Km². The country is almost surrounded by Senegal except at its coast. As of 2023 population projections, the total population of the Gambia is at 2,413,403. The population density is 176.1 per square kilometer and the overall life expectancy is 62. The Gambia is comprised of several ethnic groups, one-third of which is Mandinka, followed by Fula, Wolof, and Jola. The official language is English and about 95% of the population is Muslim. The population structure is a rapidly growing one with a growth rate of 1.86. It is comprised of a small proportion of people in old age, with most of the people between 15 and 64 years of age.

The country is divided into 7 health regions which include Western Region one (WR1), Western Region Two (WR2), Lower River Region (LRR), North Bank East (NBE), North Bank West (NBW), Central River Region (CRR) and Upper River Region (URR). This study was conducted in Central River Region, which is the biggest region by land size. Western region 1 and 2 are the most populated regions in the country and are mostly urban, while the remaining five regions comprise mostly rural settlements.

There are four broad components to the health care delivery system in The Gambia: Central referral hospitals; the village-based Primary Health Care (PHC) or Village Health Service (VHS); the facility-based Basic Health Service (BHS); and the Regional Health Directorate (RHD) that supervises and supply the BHS and the VHS. There are three major referral hospitals in the Gambia, located in Banjul, Farafenni and Bansang, that provide tertiary care for patients. Primary health care villages are selected from those with health facilities.

Figure 3.1: Map of the Gambia

3.1.2 Study Site

The study was conducted within households in Central River Region (CRR). This is the sixth region of the Gambia. It is located inland country, and it is populated mostly by rural settlements. The major activities in CRR include petty trade and farming activities which include groundnut and rice cultivation and animal farming. It has a total population of 274,260 (as of 2023 MOH population projections) and a projected under-five population of 43,059. The region constitutes two local government areas and ten districts. Each LGA comprises 5 districts which include: (Janjanbureh LGA located in the North and Kuntaur LGA located in the South). Districts in Janjanbureh LGA include Fulladou West, Janjanbureh, Bansang, Niamina East and Niamina West. Districts in Kuntaur LGA include Lower Saloum, Upper Saloum, Niani, Nianija, and Sami.

The region has a total of 28 health facilities, which include both government and private facilities, health posts and community clinics. The health system operates from the Regional Health Directorate (RHD) to health facilities and then to the community. The RHD monitors and manages the activities of all health facilities within the region. The health facilities are responsible for implementing the preventive and curative medicine such as antenatal clinics, and routine immunization clinics for children. The health facilities supervise all community engagements and activities and then report to the RHD. Community level stakeholders involve specific people who are selected and trained in basic health service delivery. They report all their activities to health facilities.

Figure 3.2: Map of Central River Region

3.2 Study design

A community-based cross-sectional study was conducted among caregivers of under-five children in Central River Region from September to October 2023. A mixed method of quantitative and qualitative was used to conduct the study.

3.3 Study population

The study population comprised caregivers of under-five children within the household living in Central River Region. The caregivers were either the biological parents or any individual who was directly involved in the care of an under-five child who got sick four weeks prior to the study. The caregivers may be mothers, fathers, siblings, housemaids, grandparents, neighbours, foster parents, relatives, or as it exists during the study. All participants were selected based on the child who had symptoms of a febrile illness four weeks prior to the study.

3.4 Eligibility criteria

3.4.1 Inclusion criteria

All caregivers of under-five children who showed symptoms of any febrile illnesses four weeks prior to the study were included in the study. If a caregiver had more than one under-five child, the child who had the most recent febrile illness was included in the study.

3.4.2 Exclusion criteria

Caregivers of under-five children who have hearing difficulties or health conditions that will deter their participation in the study.

3.5 Sample size estimation

The sample size was calculated using the single proportion formula for cross-sectional studies.

$$n = \frac{z_{(1-\alpha/2)}^2 pq}{d^2}$$

$Z\alpha$ = standard normal deviate corresponding with a confidence level of 95% = 1.96

p = prevalence of self-medication among caregivers of under-five children in rural areas, Ferlo, Senegal = 61.2% (0.612) (Mareme Sougou, 2017)

$q = (1-p) = 0.388$

$d = \text{margin of error} = 0.05$

$n = (1.96^2) 0.612 \times 0.388 \div (0.05^2)$

$n = 365$

After adjusting for a non-response rate (f) of 10%, the final size was $(n \times 1/1-f)$

Therefore, the minimum sample size was, $N = 406$

3.6 Sampling procedure

A multi-stage cluster sampling was used to recruit eligible participants for the study. Central River Region (CRR) was purposively selected out of the seven health regions of the Gambia. A simple random sampling was used to select 3 districts out of the 10 from Central River Region through balloting. Each district served as a cluster. All villages within the three districts (clusters) were included in the sampling frame. 30% of villages were randomly selected from each of the three districts and proportionate sampling was used to determine how many households to select from each village with respect to the total population of the selected districts. A simple random sampling then was used to select eligible respondents (caregivers of under-five children) from each household. If a household contains more than one eligible respondent, balloting was used to select one respondent. This method was repeated for all the selected villages. Fulladu West has a total population of 108,388 from which 293 participants were sampled using a simple random sample. Niani has a total population of 34,550 of which 94 participants were selected. 19 participants were selected from Niamina Dankunku which has a total population of 7, 060.

Table 3.1: Proportionate sampling of the three selected districts [N =406]

NO	DISTRICTS	TOTAL POPULATION IN THE DISTRICT (N)	PROPORTIONATE SAMPLE SIZE CALCULATED P(n/N*406)	PERCENTAGE (%)
1	Fulladu West	108,388	293	72
2	Niani	34,550	94	23
3	Niamina Dankunku	7,060	19	5
	Total	149,998	406	100

3.7 Data Collection Instruments

Quantitative instrument

Data were collected using semi-structured questionnaires (Appendix II). The questionnaires were adapted from previous studies by (Wen, Lieber, Wan, and Hong, 2011; Eldalo et al., 2013; Aqeel et al., 2014; Tarcuic, Stanescu, Diaconu, Paduraru, Duduciuc, and Diaconescu, 2020; Tarcuic, Pleşca, Duduciuc, Gimiga, Tătăranu, Herdea, Ion, and Diaconescu, 2022) and modified to best suit the objectives of this study.

- The quantitative methods were completed using Kobo Collect data collection software and the questionnaires were pretested in rural areas of Western Region Two, which has similar settlements and populations to Central River Region.

Qualitative instruments

The qualitative methods were conducted using guides (Appendix III) and audio records were taken to capture all the discussions.

3.8 Training of research assistants

Four research assistants were recruited and trained on the quantitative questionnaire. They were taken through all the questions one by one for familiarity. The training was conducted in a day considering the experience of the assistants in data collection. They were allowed to test the questionnaire and raise/make queries during the training. The research assistants were all fluent in the 3 major local languages (Mandinka, Wolof, and Fula) in the study site. Their language fluency was tested by directing them to perform a simulation exercise and

administer the questions in all the languages, one after the other. Upon completing the training, the research assistants were deployed to the 3 selected districts in the region based on the district that best suits their language in order to minimize language barriers.

3.9 Pretesting

The quantitative questionnaire was pretested between September 11th and 15th among caregivers of under-five children in Western Region Two. A total of 20 participants were recruited for the pretest and were conveniently selected prior to obtaining informed consent. Kobo collect was used to administer the questionnaire. The pretest data was analyzed descriptively using SPSS version 30.

3.10 Data collection

Quantitative method

Data were collected through an interviewer-administered questionnaire. The quantitative questionnaire was divided into four sections intended to answer each of the specific objectives of the study: these include:

- A. Sociodemographic characteristics
- B. Knowledge of caregivers of under-five children on signs/symptoms of childhood febrile illnesses
- C. Self-medication practices for perceived febrile illnesses
- D. Factors influencing self-medication of under-five children for perceived febrile illnesses

Qualitative method

The Qualitative questions comprised:

- A. Socio-demographic characteristics
- B. Reasons for self-medication of under five children for perceive febrile illnesses

The qualitative methods for the study were in three segments using open-ended questions (Appendix III).

1. Three Focus group discussions were carried out among caregivers of under-five children who practiced self-medication four weeks prior to the study. A total of 24 participants were conveniently recruited from 3 villages (Bansang, Brikama Ba, and Kuntaur). being the biggest villages in the 3 districts samples for the study. Each of

the focus groups consisted of 8 participants. There were 21 females and 3 males with a minimum age of 18 and maximum age of 45 years. The focus group discussions were conducted using focus group guides (Appendix III) and the interviews were audio recorded.

2. In-depth interviews were carried out among caregivers of under-five children who practiced self-medication four weeks prior to the study. 3 participants, consisting of 2 females and a male, were conveniently selected and interviewed from 3 villages (Bansang, Brikama Ba, and Kuntaur), being the biggest villages in the 3 districts sampled for the study. The participants' age were 29, 31 and 40. The interviews were conducted using interview guides (Appendix III) and the interviews were audio recorded.

3.11 Variable definition

Independent variables:

Age: Age was classified into two: The age of the caregiver in years and the age of the child in months. Age of the caregiver was categorized into 3 (15-24, 25-34, and 35 above). Age of the child was also categorized into 3 (1-11, 12-35, and 36-59).

Sex: The sex both caregiver and child were categorized into male and female.

Level of Education: The level of education of the caregivers was categorized in 4 (No formal education, Primary, Secondary, and Tertiary).

Marital status: The marital status of the caregivers was categorized into 4 (Single, Married, Widowed, Divorced, and Separated). This was used for the descriptive analysis. It was further as re-classified into 2 categories (Single and married). "Married" was maintained and "single" was incorporated with "Widowed, Divorced, and Separated".

Employment status: Employment status was categorized into 2 (Employed and Not Employed).

Income: The income of caregivers was defined by the minimum monthly wage of the Gambia (D1500). The Income of caregivers was categorized into 3 (<1500, 1500-3000, and 3001 above).

Dependent variables:

Measurement of Knowledge: The knowledge of caregivers was determined by scoring all the 9 questions under the knowledge section of the questionnaire. Each of the questions had multiple options, some of which were multiple response questions. Each correct option was scored as “1” while a wrong option was scored as “0”.

Self-medication practice: Self-medication practice was determined by recoding the question that asked about the first action taken to treat the illness the child suffered from. All the responses that said (visit a health facility, visit a traditional healer, and visit a healthcare provider at home) were recorded as “Not self-medicate” while all the responses that said (“Self-medicated with drugs bought from pharmacy” and “Gave child left-over drugs”) were recorded “Self- medicated”.

3.12 Data Management

Data were cleaned and analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 20 and Stata version 12. Data were summarized using descriptive statistics such as frequency tables, proportions, and charts. Statistical tests were conducted at 95% confidence level. Chi-square was used to determine the association between the outcome (Self-medication practice) variable and explanatory (socio-economic factors) variables. Logistic regression was carried out to determine the participants’ socio-demographic and socio-economic factors that influence their self-medication practice. Odds ratios and confidence intervals were used to summarize the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable.

3.13 Data Analysis

Quantitative data analysis

Data were analyzed based on the objectives of the study. The quantitative questionnaire contained five different sections meant to answer each of the specific objectives. Section A comprised the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents which were analyzed using frequency and percentage. Section B comprised the knowledge of caregivers on childhood febrile illnesses which contained 9 questions and each question contained multiple choice options. Based on these, the overall knowledge score of caregivers was calculated by summing the scores for all correct responses. A correct response was scored as “1” and an incorrect response as “0”. There was a total of 9 questions with the highest possible

knowledge score of 37. A score ≤ 18 was graded as poor knowledge, while a score ≥ 19 was graded as good knowledge. SPSS version 20 was used to carry out the scoring. The scoring system was adopted from a study conducted by (Hareed, 2018). Section C comprised 4 questions on the Experience of caregivers on the most recent febrile illness the child had four weeks prior to the study. Section D comprised 6 questions on self-medication practices of caregivers towards the most recent febrile illnesses the under-five children suffered from. Section D contained 5 questions on factors that influence self-medication practice among the caregivers.

Qualitative data analysis

Qualitative data comprised 3 focus group discussions with 8 questions each, and 3 in-depth interviews with 11 questions each. Each focus group discussion was completed within 2 hours while each of the in-depth interviews were completed in about 30 minutes. The respondents comprised both males and females who were asked questions about their opinions and experiences with regards to self-medicating their children. The sessions were recorded using a Nokia phone and all individual responses were also noted with pen and paper and categorized into themes based on the questions and similarities in responses.

A. Focus group discussions

All the audio recordings from the three focus group discussions were transcribed into verbatim texts, coded and grouped into themes based on the objectives of the study. Each theme contained similar questions in the same category and all similar responses are analysed a single code. Each focus group was audio recorded using a Nokia phone, coded and analyzed separately, before a final analysis was conducted combining all three focus group results. Atlas.ti a qualitative data analysis software package, was used to sort all codes into appropriate themes. The themes were then used to report the findings narrated by the respondents.

B. In-depth interviews

Each of the three in-depth interviews were audio-recorded using a Nokia phone. A separate questionnaire was used for each of the interviews and the audio records were transcribed into verbatim text and analyzed based on each question and all similar responses were coded into one and grouped into themes based on the objectives of the study. Each theme represented questions within the same category. Atlas.ti a qualitative data analysis software package was used to sort all codes into appropriate themes. These themes were used to make the final report of the narrated responses.

3.14 Ethical considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the Gambia government / MRC joint Ethics Committee through the Scientific Coordinating Committee (SCC), with project ID 29505.

3.14.1 Beneficence and Non-maleficence

No harm was caused to the participants during the course of the study. The results were also disseminated to both the participants and key stakeholders.

3.14.2 Informed consent

A detailed written informed consent was obtained from all participants. Participants were informed about the choice to participate and withdraw from the study at any time.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS

4.1 Socio-demographic characteristics

Table 4.1 shows the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents. A total of 406 participants were interviewed for the study. Of the total participants, 372 (91.6%) were the biological parents of the under five children sampled for the study. The mean age (SD) of the participants was 31.1(9.6) years, within the range (15-74) years. The mean age (SD) of children was 20.1 (15.4) months. The majority 330(81.3%) of the participants were females, most 333(82.0%) were currently married, and the dominant ethnic group was Wolof, 145(35.7%), followed by Mandinka, 115(28.3%) and Fula 102(25.1%).

Table 4.1: Socio-demographic characteristics of respondents [N=406]

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Sex of caregiver		
Female	330	81.3
Male	76	18.7
Age of caregiver (Years)		
15-24	81	20.0
25-34	215	53.0
35 above	110	27.1
Sex of child		
Female	193	47.5
Male	213	52.5
Age of child (Months)		
1-11	149	36.7
12-35	176	43.3
36-59	81	20.0
Marital Status		
Single	73	18
Currently married	333	82.0
Relationship of caregiver with child		
Mother	303	74.6
Father	69	17.0
Guardian	34	8.4
Ethnicity		
Wolof	145	35.7
Mandinka	115	28.3
Fula	102	25.1
**Others	44	10.8

****Others (Ethnicity): Serahuli, Jola, Serer, and Balanta**

4.2: Socio-economic characteristics of respondents

Table 4.2 shows the socio-economic characteristics of the respondents. A total of 177(43.6%) respondents had no formal education, 304(74.9%) were unemployed and 148(50.2%) earned more than the monthly minimum wage.

Table 4.2: Socio-economic characteristics of respondents [N=406]

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Level of education		
No formal education	177	43.6
Primary	75	18.5
Secondary	86	21.2
Tertiary	68	16.7
Work status		
Not Employed	304	74.9
Employed	102	25.1
Occupation		
Civil servant	78	19.2
Business	68	16.7
Housewife/stay at home parent	182	44.8
**Others	78	19.2
Caregiver income per month (In Dalasi)		
<1500	86	29.2
1500-3000	61	20.7
3001 above	148	50.2

****Others (Occupation): Farming, Student, House help, and Nanny**

4.3 Sources of information on childhood febrile illnesses

Figure 4.1 shows the respondents' sources of information on childhood febrile illnesses. Majority 208(51.2%) of the caregivers sought information from friends, followed by family members 147(36.2%) and doctor 94(23.2%).

Figure 4.1: Sources of information on childhood febrile illnesses

4.4 Knowledge of caregivers on common childhood febrile illnesses

Table 4.3 shows respondents' knowledge on childhood febrile illnesses. Majority 334(82.3%) of the respondents were able to mention fresh cold as a childhood illness, followed by malaria 171(42.1%), Gastroenteritis 165(40.5%), Skin infection 135(33.3%) and Pneumonia 121(29.8%). Respondents who said Bacteria cause childhood illnesses were 240(59.1%), followed by Germs 199(49.0%) and viruses 175(43.1%). The majority 363(89.4%) of the respondents said that an increase in body temperature is an indication of an illness, which is followed by crying too much 223(54.9%), changes in feeding and changes in behaviour 133(32.8%). Respondents who believe that fever can be transmitted from one child to another 200(49.3%), 379(93.3%) believe that antibiotics are necessary in the treatment of fever and that all febrile illnesses should be treated with antibiotics 283(69.7%).

Table 4.3: Knowledge of caregivers on common childhood febrile illnesses [N=406]

Variable (Multiple responses)	Yes	Percentage
Name common childhood febrile illnesses		
Fresh cold/upper respiratory tract infections	334	82.3
Malaria	171	42.1
Gastroenteritis	165	40.5
Skin infection	135	33.3
Pneumonia	121	29.8
Measles	40	9.9
**Others	39	9.6
Nappy rash	25	6.2
Eye infection	17	4.2
Injury/trauma	7	1.7
Fever can be transmitted from one child to another		
True	200	49.3
False	206	50.7
How to tell a child is ill*		
Increase in body temperature	363	89.4
Crying too much	223	54.9
Changes in feeding	223	54.9
Changes in behaviour	133	32.8
**Others	8	2.0
Causes of childhood febrile illnesses		
Bacteria	240	59.1
Germs	199	49.0
Viruses	175	43.1
Witches	25	6.2
Evil spirits	19	3.2
**Others	13	4.7

****Others: (Common childhood illnesses): Teething illness, Malnutrition, Meningitis and Anaemia**

****Others: (How to tell a child is ill): Reduced physical activity and red eyes**

***Multiple response**

****Others: (Causes of childhood febrile illnesses): Parasites, Fungi, Rain and Bad winds**

Knowledge of caregivers on the management and prevention of childhood febrile illnesses [N=406]

Table 4.4 shows the respondents' level of knowledge on childhood febrile illnesses. About 92.4% (375) believe that medical attention should be sought for a sick child immediately symptoms begin and 3.9% (16) believe that it should be sought when symptoms become worse. Majority of respondents' opinions on actions to take for a sick child was to visit a health facility 373 (91.9%), followed by visiting a pharmacy/drug store 18(4.4%). Their knowledge on how to prevent childhood illnesses include good hygiene 316(77.8%), Vaccination 239(58.9%), using preventive measures 185(45.6%) and Healthy and balanced diet 182(44.8%).

Table 4.4: Knowledge of caregivers on the management and prevention of childhood febrile illnesses [N=406]

Variable	Yes	Percentage
Antibiotics are necessary in the treatment of fever		
True	379	93.3
False	27	6.7
All febrile illnesses should be treated with antibiotics		
True	283	69.7
False	123	30.3
When to seek medical attention for a child sick with a febrile illness		
Immediately symptoms begin	375	92.4
When symptoms become worse	16	3.9
When there are no medications at home	7	1.7
When the parent is not busy	4	1.0
Others	4	1.0
Actions taken when a child is sick with a febrile illness		
Visit a health facility	373	91.9
Visit a pharmacy/drug store	18	4.4
Treat the child at home	12	3.0
Visit a traditional healer	3	0.7
How to prevent childhood febrile illnesses*		
Good hygiene	316	77.8
Vaccination	239	58.9
Using preventive measures (e.g. bed nets, chemoprophylaxis)	185	45.6
Healthy and balanced diet	182	44.8
Exercise	30	7.4

***Multiple response**

4.5 Overall knowledge of caregivers on childhood febrile illnesses

Figure 4.3 shows the overall knowledge of caregivers based on their responses on childhood febrile illnesses. About 165(40.6%) of the caregivers had good knowledge of childhood febrile illnesses while 241(59.4%) had poor knowledge. The mean knowledge score of the caregivers was 12.7 (SD=3.5) points.

Figure 4.2: Overall knowledge of caregivers on childhood febrile illnesses

4.6 Caregivers' experience of the most recent febrile illness in under-five children

Table 4.5 shows the caregivers' experience of their children's most recent febrile illnesses within four weeks before the study. The most prominent signs/symptoms mentioned by the caregivers when a child had a febrile illness were fever 307(75.6%), cough/runny nose 190(46.8%) and diarrhoea 115(28.3%). Ninety (22.2%) of the respondents suspected fresh cold/upper respiratory tract infections, followed by malaria 56(13.8%) and thirdly, chest infection/pneumonia 47(11.6%). The majority 302(74.4%) of caregivers visited a health facility to treat the illness, while 87(21.5%) either self-medicated the child with drugs bought from a pharmacy or leftover drugs from a previous illness.

Table 4.5: Caregivers' experience of the most recent febrile illness in under-five children [N=406]

Variable	Yes	Percentage
Signs/symptoms of child's most recent febrile illness		
Fever	307	75.6
Cough/runny nose	190	46.8
Diarrhoea	115	28.3
Difficulty in breathing	46	11.3
Vomiting	87	21.4
Rashes	60	14.8
Weakness	54	13.3
**Others	14	3.4
Suspected illness when the mentioned symptoms started		
Fresh cold/upper respiratory tract infections	90	22.2
Malaria	56	13.8
Chest infection/Pneumonia	47	11.6
Gastroenteritis	37	9.1
Skin infection	29	7.1
**Others	11	2.7
Measles	6	1.5
Nappy rash	1	0.2
Injury/trauma	1	0.2
First action taken to treat the illness		
Visit a health facility where the child was treated	302	74.4
Self-medicate with drugs bought from pharmacy	64	15.8
Gave the child leftover drugs from previous illness	23	5.7
Visit a traditional healer/marabout	11	2.7
Visit a healthcare provider at home	6	1.5

****Others: (Signs/symptoms of child's most recent febrile illness): Painful urination, Sunken eyes, yellow eyes, seizures, and swollen gums.**

****Others: (Suspected illness when the mentioned symptoms started): UTI and Jaundice**

4.7 Caregivers' self-medication practices for the febrile illness in the child

Table 4.6 shows caregivers' self-medication practices. The prevalence of self-medication of under-five children was **21.43%** (87/406). Paracetamol/Ibuprofen was given to 38(9.4%) of the children, cough syrup to 37(9.1%) and antibiotics 19(4.7%). The sources of medications mostly mentioned by caregivers were pharmacy 65(15.0%) and leftover drugs 20(4.9%). Cough/runny nose was self-medicated the most 45(11.1%), followed by fever 30(7.4%) and then diarrhoea 21(5.2%). When the respondents were asked how they normally determine the appropriate dosage of a medication before administering it, 33(8.1%) said they usually read the label instructions, 22(5.4%) said they will ask a family member, friend, or neighbour, and 18(4.4%) mentioned asking a pharmacist.

Table 4.6: Caregivers' self-medication practices for the perceived febrile illness in the child [N = 87]

Variable	Yes	Percentage
Medications administered to child		
Paracetamol/Ibuprofen	38	9.4
Cough syrup	37	9.1
Antibiotics	19	4.7
Oral rehydration solution	13	3.2
Teething syrup	9	2.2
Traditional/herbal remedies	5	1.2
Antimalarial drugs	4	1
**Others	4	1
Sources of medications		
Pharmacy	65	16
Leftover drugs	20	4.9
Neighbours	4	1
Family members	3	0.7
Friends	3	0.7
Drug hawkers	2	0.5
Traditional healer/marabout	2	0.5
Signs/symptoms self-medicated most		
Fever	30	7.4
Cough/runny nose	45	11.1
Diarrhoea	21	5.2
Rash	14	3.4
Vomiting	12	3.0
Difficulty in breathing	1	0.2
Weakness	1	0.2
**Others	1	0.2
Determining the appropriate dosage of medication for the child		
Reading the label instructions	33	8.1
Asking a family member, friend, or neighbour	22	5.4
Asking a pharmacist	18	4.4
Guess the dosage based on previous use	13	3.2
Consulting a healthcare professional	1	0.2

****Others (Medications administered): Anti-fungal cream**

****Others (Signs/symptoms self-medicated most): Sneezing**

Figure 4.3: Medications administered to under-five children by their caregivers for perceived febrile illnesses

4.8 Factors associated with self-medication by caregivers of under-five children with febrile illnesses

Table 4.7 shows the factors associated with self-medication of under-five children. Respondents who self-medicated their children backed it up with reasons such as long waiting hours at the health facility 35(8.6%), knowledge of symptoms of the illness 33(8.1%) and that the illness of the child was too minor 31(7.6%). Others mentioned far distance to the health facility 20(4.9%) and experience in self-medication 17(4.2%). The usual sources of self-medication information that the respondents relied on most were family members 61(15%), and friends 46(11.3%). About 66(16.3%) of the respondents were very confident with these sources of information and 13(3.2%) were somehow confident.

Table 4.7: Factors associated with self-medication of under-five children with febrile illnesses by their caregivers [N=87]

Variable	Yes	Percentage
Reasons for self-medication		
Long waiting hours at the health	35	8.6
Knowledge of symptoms	33	8.1
Minor illness of the child	31	7.6
Far distance to the health facility	20	4.9
Experience in self-medication	17	4.2
Financial constraints	12	3
Availability of leftover drugs	9	2.2
**Others	8	2
Bad attitude of healthcare workers	7	1.7
Distance from place of medication/s to place of residence? (In meters)		
<100	22	5.4
100-500	52	12.8
501-1000	4	1.0
1000 above	5	1.2
Distance from nearest hospital/health facility to place of residence? (In meters)		
<100	5	1.2
100-500	47	11.6
501-1000	27	6.7
1000 above	6	1.5
Common sources of self-medication information		
Family members	61	15
Friends	46	11.3
Leaflet in the pack of drug	17	4.2
Google/internet search	16	3.9
Neighbours	15	3.7
pharmacist	12	3
Doctor	9	2.2
**Others	9	2.2
Traditional healer/marabout	5	1.2
Community/Online groups of parents from forums	5	1.2
Television	3	0.7
Social media	2	0.4
Radio	1	0.2
Health talks during vaccination clinics	1	0.2

***Others: (Reasons for self-medication): No drugs at health facility**

***Others: (Common sources of self-medication information): Nurse**

Figure 4.5: Reasons for self-medication of under-five children by their caregivers

Figure 4.6: Common sources of self-medication information

4.9 Bivariate analysis between socio-demographic factors and self-medication practice

Table 4.8 shows the association between socio-demographic factors and self-medication. Age of caregiver ($\chi^2=17.546$; $p<0.001$) and Age of child ($\chi^2=43.121$; $p<0.001$) were significantly associated with self-medication.

Table 4.8: Bivariate analysis between socio-demographic factors and self-medication practice

Variable	Self-medication		χ^2	p-value
	No n (%)	Yes n (%)		
Gender of caregiver				
Female	263 (82.4)	67 (77.0)	1.326	0.249
Male	56 (17.6)	20 (23.0)		
Gender of child				
Female	146 (45.8)	47 (54.0)	1.858	0.172
Male	173 (54.2)	40 (46.0)		
Age of caregiver (Years)				
15 – 24	63 (19.7)	18 (20.7)	17.546	<0.001*
25 – 34	184 (57.7)	31 (35.6)		
35 above	72 (22.6)	38 (43.70)		
Age of child (Months)				
0-11	138 (43.3)	11 (12.6)	43.121	<0.001*
12-35	136 (42.6)	40 (46.0)		
36 – 59	45 (14.1)	36 (41.4)		
Level of education				
No formal education	142 (44.5)	35 (40.2)	5.804	0.122
Primary	54 (16.9)	21 (24.1)		
Secondary	64 (20.1)	22 (25.3)		
Tertiary	59 (18.5)	9 (10.3)		

4.10 Bivariate analysis between knowledge of childhood febrile illnesses and self-medication practice

Table 4.9 shows the association between knowledge of childhood febrile illnesses and self-medication practice. There was no significant association between knowledge of childhood febrile illnesses and the practice of self-medication ($\chi^2=0.683$; $p=0.408$).

Table 4.9: Bivariate analysis between knowledge of childhood febrile illnesses and self-medication practice

Self-medication	Knowledge n (%)		χ^2	p-value
	Poor	Good		
No	186 (58.31)	133 (41.69)	0.683	0.408
Yes	55 (63.22)	32 (36.78)		
Total	241(121.53)	165 (78.47)		

4.11 Bivariate analysis between selected variables and self-medication practice

Table 4.10 shows all the selected variables that were significantly associated with self-medication practice. Self-medication was associated with obtaining information on childhood illnesses from Friends ($\chi^2=17.785$; $P<0.001$), Family members ($\chi^2=5.397$; $p=0.020$), Neighbours ($\chi^2=5.397$; $p=0.020$) and Radio ($\chi^2=4.968$; $p=0.026$). The reasons associated with self-medication include knowledge of symptoms of an illness ($\chi^2=12.315$; $p<0.001$), long waiting hours at the health facility ($\chi^2=13.417$; $p<0.001$) and bad attitude of healthcare workers ($\chi^2=5.396$; $p=0.020$). The sources of self-mediation information found to be associated with self-medication practice were Friends ($\chi^2=12.172$; $p<0.001$), Family members ($\chi^2=13.685$; $p<0.001$), Pharmacist ($\chi^2=5.995$; $p=0.014$), neighbours ($\chi^2=18.932$; $p<0.001$) community/online groups of parents ($\chi^2=10.315$; $p=0.001$), and traditional healer/marabout ($\chi^2=10.315$; $p=0.001$).

Table 4.10: Bivariate analysis between selected variables and self-medication practice

Variable	Self-medication		χ^2	p-value
	No (%)	Yes (%)		
Source of information on childhood febrile illnesses				
Friends				
No	239 (76.1)	25 (12.6)	17.785	<0.001
Yes	80 (87.0)	62 (29.8)		
Family members				
No	214 (82.6)	45 (17.4)	6.983	0.008
Yes	105 (71.4)	42 (28.6)		
Neighbours				
No	272 (80.7)	65 (19.3)	5.397	0.020
Yes	47 (68.1)	22 (31.9)		
Radio				
No	239 (76.1)	75 (23.9)	4.968	0.026
Yes	80 (87.0)	12 (13.0)		
Reasons for self-medication				
Knowledge of symptoms				
No	301 (80.7)	72 (19.3)	12.315	<0.001
Yes	18 (54.5)	15 (45.5)		
Long waiting hours at the health facility				
No	300 (80.9)	71 (19.1)	13.417	<0.001
Yes	19 (54.3)	16 (45.7)		
Bad attitude of healthcare workers				
No	316 (79.2)	83 (20.8)	5.396	0.020
Yes	3 (42.9)	4 (57.1)		
Source of information on self-medication				
Friends				
No	292 (81.1)	68 (18.9)	12.172	<0.001
Yes	27 (58.7)	19 (41.3)		
Pharmacist				
No	313 (79.4)	81 (20.6)	5.995	0.014
Yes	6 (50.0)	6 (50.0)		
Neighbours				
No	314 (80.3)	77 (19.7)	18.932	<0.001
Yes	5 (33.3)	10 (66.7)		
Traditional healer/marabout				
No	318 (99.7)	83 (95.4)	10.315	0.001
Yes	1 (0.3)	4 (4.6)		
Community/Online groups of parents from forums				
No	318 (99.7)	83 (95.4)	10.315	0.001
Yes	1 (0.3)	4 (4.6)		
Family members				
No	282 (81.7)	83 (20.7)	13.685	<0.001
Yes	37 (60.7)	4 (80.0)		

4.12 Binary logistic regression for factors associated with self-medication practice for perceived febrile illnesses among under-five children

Table 4.11a shows the factors found to be associated with self-medication practice at Chi square analysis inputted into the binary logistic regression. It was found that caregivers within the age category 25-34 were less likely to practice self-medication than the younger age categories (aOR=0.394; CI=0.183 - 0.849; P=0.017). The odds of self-medication were higher among children who are ≥ 3 years than those who are younger (aOR=9.435; CI=3.886 - 22.904; p=<0.001). Respondents who received information from Friends on childhood illnesses were more likely to self-medicate than those who did not (aOR=2.564; CI=1.406 - 4.672; P=0.002).

Table 4.11a: Predictors of self-medication practice among caregivers of under-five children

Variables	aOR	p-Value	95% Confidence Interval (CI)
Age of caregiver (Years)			
15 -24 (ref)	1		
25 -34	0.394	0.017*	0.183 - 0.849
35 above	0.805	0.596	0.849 - 1.793
Age of child (Months)			
0 – 11 (ref)	1		
12 – 35	3.087	0.006*	1.381 - 6.897
36 - 59	9.435	<0.001*	3.886 - 22.904
Source of information on childhood febrile illnesses			
Radio			
No (ref)	1		
Yes	0.7946	0.550	0.374 - 1.689
Family members			
No (ref)	1		
Yes	0.938	0.839	0.507 - 1.735
Neighbours			
No (ref)	1		
Yes	1.516	0.264	0.729 - 3.150
Friends			
No (ref)	1		
Yes	2.564	0.002*	1.406 - 4.672

***Significant at p<0.05**

Predictors of self-medication practice among caregivers of under-five children

Table 4.11b shows the factors found to be associated with self-medication practice at Chi square analysis inputted into the binary logistic regression. Respondents who received information on self-medication from neighbours (aOR=7.008; CI=1.554 - 31.591; P=0.011) and pharmacist (aOR=4.746; CI=1.085 - 20.756; P=0.039) were more likely to self-medicate their under-five children.

Table 4.11b: Predictors of self-medication practice among caregivers of under-five children

Variable	aOR	p-value	95% Confidence interval (CI)
Sources of Self-medication information			
Neighbours			
No (ref)	1		
Yes	7.008	0.011*	1.554 - 31.591
Friends			
No (ref)	1		
Yes	0.715	0.519	0.2582 - 1.981
Pharmacist			
No (ref)	1		
Yes	4.746	0.039*	1.085 - 20.756
Traditional healer			
No (ref)	1		
Yes	4.277	0.247	0.364 - 50.191
Community/online groups of parents			
No (ref)	1		
Yes	4.229	0.247	0.368 - 48.612
Family members			
No (ref)	1		
Yes	0.744	0.580	0.261 - 2.121

***Significant at p<0.05**

4.13 Findings from Qualitative interviews

4.13.1 Focus group discussions

A total of 24 participants (21 females and 3 males) were interviewed from three villages for the focus group discussions. Each of the 3 groups consisted of 8 participants. The minimum age was 18 and maximum age 45.

Themes and Key Findings

Theme 1: Knowledge on signs/symptoms of childhood febrile illnesses

Subtheme: Fever, Cough, Diarrhoea, Runny nose and Vomiting

Participants were asked to name the most common signs/symptoms that under-five children often present and the majority mentioned fever, cough, runny nose, diarrhoea, and vomiting,

- *Children in our village always have fever and diarrhoea” (Female, Age 20, Address Bansang).*
- *My child had a Fresh cold. The nose was getting blocked, and she had a high fever”.* (Female, Age 40, Address Kuntaur).

Theme 2: Self-medication practices

Subtheme: Leftover drugs

When the participants were asked about how they treat their children’s illnesses, majority said that their first line of treatment is to give leftover drugs. And if the illness persists, some said they will buy drugs from a pharmacy while others said that they will visit a health facility.

- *“Most of the caregivers in this village never run out of drugs. We always make sure to keep them in case a child suddenly falls ill. It helps before you prepare to go to a health center” (Female, Age 55, Address Brikama Ba)*
- *“Sometimes if a child gets ill and the caregiver is too busy, she will just rush to a neighbour whose child had been suffering from a similar condition to beg for leftover drugs” (Female, Age 37, Address Bansang).*

Theme 3: Sources of Information on self-medication

Subtheme: Family members and friends

The most frequently named sources of information when it comes to self-medicating their children were family members and friends. Few mentioned neighbours and pharmacist.

- *“I usually seek information from family, members, friends and neighbours”. (Male, Age 33, Address Brikama Ba).*
- *“My family always advise me on what treatment to give my child whenever he is sick. Sometimes I ask my friends what to do”. (Female, Age 31, Address Kuntaur).*

Theme 4: Reasons/motivation for Self-Medication

Subtheme: No drugs at the health facilities

Almost all participants pointed out that it is pointless to visit a health facility since you will end up buying drugs from a pharmacy/drugs store.

- *“The health centre is far and whenever you go there, they will refer you to the pharmacy to buy medications”. (Male, Age 29, Address Kuntaur).*
- *“I hate going to a health facility whenever my child is ill. Because the nurses will waste your time and then ask you to buy the drugs”. (Female, Age 29, Address Brikama Ba).*

Subtheme: Long waiting hours at health facilities

Majority of the participant expressed their dissatisfaction with the health system stating that some people will be on the queue for hours while the child is suffering.

- *“Your child will be so sick and crying all through just for you to visit a health facility and spend the whole day waiting to be attended”. (Female, Age 32 Address Kuntaur).*
- *“We often do not have a choice than go to drug stores or use leftover drugs when our children are sick because going to a health facility will even make the child’s condition worse due to the amount of time you wait before you are attended to” (Female, Age 37, Address Brikama Ba).*

Subtheme: Past experience in self-medication

Some of the respondent pointed out that the reason why they are self-medicating their under-five children is because they have been doing it over the years and they always succeed in treating the supposed illnesses.

- *“I have been treating my children at home for years now and I know a lot of medications used to treat childhood illnesses” (Female, Age 40, Address Bansang).*

- *“When it comes to children and their illnesses, I am very good at treating them because I have been doing it even before I got my children” (Female, Age 34, Address Kuntaur).*

Theme 5: Knowledge of potential risks of self-medication

Subtheme: Self-medication can cause drug addiction

The participants stated that those who are too engaged in self-medication of children to some extent perceive it as a way of life and will tend to treat every unusual sign as an illness and consequently lead to frequent self-medication.

- *“Too much self-medication is not the best practice because when a child’s body gets used to medicines, it will be very difficult to treat their illnesses because the blood will recognize the medicine and reject it” (Female, Age 40, Address Kuntaur).*
- *“What I know is that some women will even deliberately drug their children to sleep when they want to attend programs because of ignorance and as the child grows, they become drug resistant and suffer from a lot of sicknesses” (Male, Age 35, Address Bansang).*

Theme 6: Experience in potential risks of self-medication

Subtheme: Overdose of child

Some of the participants shared their opinions and experiences about the negative effects of self-medicating a child. Among these include overdosing a child due to lack of prescription or one’s belief that they possess good knowledge of self-medication.

- *“Overdosing a child is something I will never repeat because it almost cost my child’s life. I gave him more than the doses that the pharmacy prescribed because his symptoms were getting worse, not knowing that it will harm him” (Female, Age 25, Address Brikama Ba).*
- *“My niece once fell ill and her mother left her in my care but she was crying too much and the mom did not tell me she had already given the child medicine, so I decided to give her but after some time white liquid started to come out from her mouth and when we took her to the hospital the nurse checked her and said it was an overdose of medicine” (Female, Age 30, Address Bansang).*

Subtheme: Complications from drug interactions

When the participants were asked about their past negative experiences with regards to self-medicating their children, about half said that their children's conditions got worse after self-medicating their children with more than one drug which were bought from drug stores.

- *“There was a time I gave my son two syrups at once and it caused his body temperature to increase”. (Female, Age 25, Address Brikama Ba).*
- *“Mixing different medications at once can be dangerous because the last time I did it when my child fell ill, she was vomiting very seriously.” (Female, Age 30, Address Kuntaur).*

4.13.2 In-depth interviews

A total of 3 Participants picked from the focus group participants, (2 females, and a male) were interviewed one-on-one to get the final insights on their self- medication practices. Their ages were 29, 31 and 40.

Themes and Key Findings

Theme 1: Knowledge on signs /symptoms of childhood febrile illnesses

Subtheme: Child suffered from Fever, vomiting and diarrhoea

- *“My child suffered from Fever, diarrhoea, Vomiting, and general body weakness. He refused to breastfeed or eat anything. The nose was also running lately”. (Male, Age 29, Address Bansang).*
- *“He suffered from fever and vomiting. His behaviour pattern changed. He was inactive”. (Female, Age 40, Address Kuntaur).*

Subtheme: I can determine an illness by the symptoms

- *“When I saw a lot of mucus coming out from her nose and the high body temperature, I knew she had a Fresh cold”. (Female, Age 31, Address Brikama Ba).*
- *“I was able to identify the illness. He had red gums and I noticed he was teething”. (Female, Age 40, Address Kuntaur).*
- *I realized that he was frequently passing watery stool, so I knew it was diarrhoea”. (Male, Age 29, Address Bansang).*

Theme 2: Self-medication practices

Subtheme: Took the child to a pharmacy/drug store

- *“I rushed him to the drugstore and bought teething syrup for him”. (Female, 40, Address Kuntaur).*
- *“I bought “Pritin and Vitamin C from the pharmacy and administered them to the child”. (Female, Age 31, Address Brikama Ba).*
- *“I first had to look closely at the signs and symptoms he manifested before I rushed him to the pharmacy”. (Male, Age 29, Address Bansang).*

Subtheme: Medications given to child

- *“I gave him teething syrup three times a day using the small cup inside the drug box, but if he is crying constantly, I usually give him the drugs more than three times a day”. (Female, Age 40, Address Kuntaur).*
- *“I gave her vitamin C tablet. One tablet per day. I also gave her pritin syrup, one spoonful every four to six hours”. (Female, Age 31, Address Brikama Ba).*
- *“I gave him ORS to be used for two days and Zinc tablets to use for fourteen days”. (Male, Age 29, Address, Bansang).*

Subtheme: Obtain medications from a drug store

- *“I usually obtain medications from family members who bought and used it but did not finish it. Sometimes I buy from the drug store”. (Female, Age 40, Address Kuntaur).*
- *“I bought ORS and Zinc tablets from a pharmacy”. (Male, Age 29, Bansang).*

Theme 3: Sources of information on self-medication

Subtheme: Obtain information from social media

- *“From Google and WhatsApp groups. We have a WhatsApp group where parents discuss issues about their children”. (Female, Age 40, Adress Kuntaur).*
- *“Phone call and social media. I will call my friends and seek advice. I also use social media platforms such as WhatsApp”. (Female, Age 31, Address Brikama Ba).*

Theme 4: Reasons/motivation for Self-Medication

Subtheme: Long waiting hours at health facility

- *“The queue is usually too long at the health center and I cannot wait because I have household chores to do at home” (Female, Age 40, Address Kuntaur).*
- *“There is a nearby pharmacy that is cheap, and the waiting period is shorter than the health facility”. (Female, Age 31, 20, Bansang).*

Subtheme: Past experience in self-medication

- *“I have four children and I have been the one treating them whenever they are ill” (Male, Age 45, Address Brikama Ba).*
- *“I grew up with my grandmother and due to her healing powers, I was able to learn few ways of treating sick children and I have been doing it for years now” (Female, Age 54, Address Kuntaur).*

Theme 5: Knowledge of potential risks of self-medication

Subtheme: Self-medication can kill

- *“Self-medication can kill especially in instances of overdose” (Female, Age 31, Address Brikama Ba).*
- *“Self-medication is unsafe and deadly” (Male, Age 29, Address Bansang).*

Theme 6: Experience in potential risks of self-medication

Subtheme: Wrong diagnosis

- *“There was a time I was treating the wrong illness. And that kept my child suffering for long” (Female, Age 40, Address Kuntaur).*
- *“I once took my child to a drugstore where she was diagnosed wrongly, and the treatment process was unnecessarily delayed”. (Female, Age 31, Address Brikama Ba).*

CHAPTER FIVE

DISCUSSION, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 DISCUSSION

Self-medication is characterised as taking prescription drugs for recurrent or chronic illnesses on an intermittent or continuous basis, or as using medication to treat symptoms on the basis of self-diagnosis. In both industrialised and developing nations, antibiotics are among the most often utilised drugs; nonetheless, they are frequently abused, particularly in environments with limited resources. Adverse effects and allergic reactions are more likely when patients are unaware of dosages, treatment plans, and other pharmaceutical characteristics (Cruz et al., 2022). This study was to determine the knowledge, practices, and reasons for self-medication of under-five children by their caregivers in Central River Region, The Gambia. A total of 406 participants were recruited within households from selected villages in 3 districts. There was a low prevalence of self-medication of under-five children by their caregivers.

The respondents in this study represent relatively a young population of caregivers of under-five children as the majority of them were aged 25-34 years, were females and were currently married as at the time of the study. These characteristics of the caregivers might be attributed to the low level of literacy reported in this study. This might have exposed them to early marriage coupled with the fact that the study site is rural. The cultural ideology about female schooling is still very common in the Gambia, particularly in rural areas. The low prevalence of self-medication among the respondents in this study could be related to poor knowledge of childhood febrile illnesses as more than half of the respondents had poor knowledge of childhood febrile illnesses. This finding is almost the same as the prevalence (22.2%) found in a population-based study conducted among caregivers of under-five children in Brazil (Pons et al., 2023). This is supported by the prevalence of self-medication (33.5%) reported by (Babalola et al., 2020), in their study conducted in Kaduna state, Nigeria. However, both findings are considerably lower than that of a Gambian study conducted in urban areas (Clarke et al., 2003), comprising both modern medicines and herbal remedies. These findings are contrary to the findings of (Omale et al., 2021), who conducted a study in rural areas of Ebonyi state, Nigeria and found that 70% of the respondents practiced self-medication of under-five children. These differences could be as a result of rural urban differentials and the level of knowledge of the caregivers of childhood febrile illnesses.

Majority of respondents had poor knowledge of childhood febrile illnesses, which can be explained by their low literacy level as some of them believed that fever can be transmitted from one child to another, and 70% believed that antibiotics can treat all febrile illnesses. A similar finding was made in a cross-sectional study in Bagamoyo district, where the parents/caregivers of under-five children had poor knowledge of antibiotic use (Simon and Kazaura, 2020). A study conducted in Riyadh City, Saudi Arabia among mothers and caregivers also revealed that their knowledge of signs/symptoms of childhood illnesses was low, with only 37% of them being able to identify at least three danger signs of disease (Abu-Shaheen et al., 2019). Contrary to these findings is a study conducted in Southwestern Nigeria by (Okunola et al., 2023), who reported that the caregivers of under-five children demonstrated an excellent broad understanding of the common childhood illnesses. These differences might be as a result of disparities in health education programs. The low level of knowledge can be highly attributed to inadequate health education programs to the caregivers of under-five children since only 15(3.7%) of the respondents said that they obtain information on childhood illnesses from health talks conducted during vaccination clinics.

The most common sources of medications mentioned by the caregivers in this study include pharmacy, leftover drugs, and neighbours. Other sources such as family members, friends, drug hawkers, and traditional healers were mentioned by less than 1% of the respondents. Drug hawkers are also suppliers of medications although their activities are illegal are usually carried out secretly. A study conducted in Tanzania found that most of the caregivers of under-five children purchased drugs from drugstores (Simon and Kazaura, 2020). This conforms with a Nigerian study conducted in rural areas of Ebonyi state which revealed that most of the caregivers of under-five children sought medications from drugstores, medicine vendors, or traditional healers (Omale et al., 2021). The most common sources of medications found among students practicing self-medication in an international university in the Gambia were drug store, friends, family members, leftover drugs and home remedies (Oriavwote and Ikwuka, 2022).

Across the globe, and among different cultures and regulations of the world, various types of medications/drugs are used for self-medication. These range from traditional and orthodox medicines. Studies conducted by (Aqeel et al., 2014; Paudel S and Aryal B, 2020) reported that the most commonly used medications in developing countries are analgesics and antipyretics (44.3%), followed by nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory medicines (36.4%), and antihistamines (8.5%). In this study, the frequently used drugs for self-medication include

analgesics (mainly paracetamol syrup or Ibuprofen syrup), antibiotics (amoxicillin), antimalarial (coartem), anti-inflammatory (piriton) and herbal remedies. The most frequently used medications by the caregivers in this study include paracetamol or ibuprofen, followed by cough syrup, and amoxicillin. This might be as a result of the high number of children who suffered from fever and cough/runny nose, which are mostly treated with paracetamol or cough syrups. This is in conformity with a study conducted among university students in the Gambia where paracetamol was used by almost half of the participants to treat minor ailments (Oriavwote and Ikwuka, 2022).

Paracetamol has been reported in a qualitative study conducted in South-western Nigeria to be the first line of treatment for most caregivers before seeking professional care for under-five children (Okunola, 2020). Similar studies conducted in several Sub-Saharan African countries have also reported a wide use of amoxicillin bought from drug stores to treat childhood illnesses (Kibuule et al., 2016; Nepal and Bhatta S, 2018; Orumpende et al., 2018; Ateshim et al., 2019). The high level of use of amoxicillin can be attributed to poor health seeking behaviours in Sub-Saharan African countries. Self-medication of under-five children using antibiotics has been reported by (Simon and Kazaura, 2020) in their study conducted among caregivers of under-five children in Bagamoyo district, Tanzania. Amoxicillin was the most used antibiotic by the caregivers to treat their children followed by cotrimazole and ampicillin/cloxacillin. A Gambian study conducted in urban areas by (Clarke et al., 2003) showed that 60% of caregivers of under-five children used modern medicines to self-medicate their children against malaria, while 16% used herbal remedies. There are implications to self-medication especially with antibiotics. Antibiotic resistance can result from the misuse or overuse of antibiotics, which renders the drugs ineffective against the microorganisms they are intended to combat. Antibiotic misuse increases the risk of side effects and reduces the medication's effectiveness (Linda I. Ogwuazor, Bisrat Hailemeskel, and Moges Abebe, 2020)

The most common illnesses self-medicated by caregivers in this study were fresh cold/upper respiratory tract infections 90(22.2%), Malaria 56(13.8%), chest infection/pneumonia 47(11.6%), Gastroenteritis 37(9.1%) and skin infection 29(7.1%). The study site is rural and has numerous mosquito breeding sites which is why malaria is very common among children. Malaria is endemic in most Sub-Saharan countries including the Gambia; hence, it is no longer seen as a serious illness leading to the increase in self-medication practice among (Clarke et al., 2003; Apetoh, Tilly, Baxerres, and Le Hesran, 2018). Due to their week

immune systems, children are also very prone to upper respiratory tract infections. A study conducted in Brazil among caregivers of under-five children revealed that the conditions for which self-medication was highly practiced include fever, cold and pain (Pons et al., 2023).

The most common sources of advice on self-medication in this study were family members and friends. Family members and friends are the closest and strongest social networks who, to a great extent, have an influence in almost every decision an individual makes. A study conducted in Delhi, India, reported that caregivers of under-five children often seek information on childhood illness from online sources, family members, neighbours, health care providers, both professional and unprofessional, and pharmacists (Pons et al., 2023). This is supported by a Gambian study conducted by (Oriavwote and Ikwuka, 2022) which found that the most common source of self-medication information for the participants was online sources. In this study, online sources of self-medication information were not frequently mentioned by the caregivers, and this might be as a result of low literacy, inadequate or poor internet connectivity in rural areas. This is in conformity with a study conducted in China among caregivers of children in rural and urban settlements, which found that caregivers living in central towns were more likely to obtain self-medication information from the internet, newspapers, and books, compared those living in rural areas (Yu et al., 2014).

From the multivariate analysis, it was revealed that age of a caregiver, age of a child, information from friends on childhood febrile illnesses and advice from neighbours and pharmacists to self-medicate under-five children are the predictors of self-medication. These findings are supported by those of study conducted by (Simon and Kazaura, 2020) among caregivers of under-five children, which found that children under the age of five are more likely to receive antibiotics than other drugs because they are more vulnerable to common respiratory, urinary tract, and diarrheal illnesses than children in other age groups. This can be influenced by the fact that children under the age of five have weaker immune systems compared to older children and can die faster or develop serious complications if their illnesses are left untreated or if treatment is delayed. They also found that age of the caregiver was significantly associated with self-medication practice, especially among younger caregivers.

The reasons for self-medication from the focus group discussions and In-depth interviews were long waiting hours, lack of drugs in health facilities and past experience in self-medication. Participants were also asked about their perceptions and past negative experiences regarding the potential risks associated with self-medication. From the interviews, some of the caregivers' said that too much of self-medication to some extent will result to drug resistance causing the body to be highly vulnerable to more infections. Other perceived risks of self-medication mentioned by the caregivers were the fact that self-medication is unsafe and deadly. The past negative experiences that caregivers mentioned include overdose of child, complications from drug interactions, and wrong diagnoses. These findings are supported by that of (Ruiz Esperanza Maria, 2010) whose study analyzed literature on dangers associated with self-medication and found that misdiagnosis, overdose, and dangerous drug interactions are the most common risks associated with self-medication.

Limitation

The limitation of the study was the high level of illiteracy among the caregivers resulting in the difficulty to recall or mention the names of medications they administered to their children four weeks prior to the study. However, we were able to use pictorials of commonly used medications in the country and probe more to help them recall or mention the local names commonly used to refer to the medications.

5.2 CONCLUSION

In this study, the prevalence of self-medication is very low, which may be explained by the poor knowledge among the caregivers on childhood febrile illnesses. The most common medications administered by the caregivers to self-medicate their under-five children include Paracetamol/Ibuprofen, cough syrup and amoxicillin. The common conditions for which self-medication was practiced include fresh cold, malaria, chest infection/pneumonia, gastroenteritis, and skin infection, The most usual sources of self-medication information were family members and friends. Age of caregiver, age of child, information from friends on childhood illnesses and self-medication advice from neighbours and pharmacists were found to be predictors of self-medication. The younger the age of a caregiver, the more likely the practice of self-medication in an under-five child. Long waiting hours, lack of drugs at health facility, and past experience with self-medication, were the reasons promoting self-medication of under-five children by their caregivers.

5.3 RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Health talks in health facilities and at the community level should be strengthened to ensure that all caregivers of under-five children especially those within the age category 15-24 years. They should be thought on how to identify danger signs of an illness in a child and know how to safely respond in case of an emergency.
2. The Ministry of Health of the Gambia should employ more health workers in rural areas to reduce waiting time of patients and ensure that there is equal, easy and affordable access to health care for all children, even those in remote villages.
3. The identified predictors of self-medication should be considered while designing policies on self-medication for febrile illnesses among under-five children in the Gambia.
4. Health care workers should be well trained on workplace etiquettes so as to improve on good attitude and relationship with patients.
5. Policies banning the indiscriminate sales of drugs especially antibiotics as over the counter drugs without professional training should be formulated.

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APPENDICES

Appendix I

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET AND INFORMED CONSENT

Study Title: Caregivers' self-medication practices for perceived febrile illnesses among under-five Children in Central River Region, the Gambia

Definitions

Self-medication

Self-medication is the use of medicines to treat self-diagnosed symptoms or the intermittent or ongoing use of prescribed drugs for chronic or recurrent diseases.

Febrile illness

It is the increase in body temperature in response to infectious diseases caused by bacteria, viruses, parasites, or fungal infections.

What is informed consent?

You are invited to take part in a research study. Participating in a research study is not the same as getting regular medical care. The purpose of normal medical care is to improve one's health. The purpose of a research study is to gather information that may be useful for the whole population in the future. It is your decision to take part and you can stop at any time without giving any reason.

Before you decide you need to understand why the study is being done and what will happen in it. Please take time to read the following information or get the information explained to you in your language. Listen carefully. You can ask questions if there is anything that you do not understand. Ask for it to be explained until you are satisfied. You may also wish to speak to your spouse, family members, or others before deciding to take part in the study.

If you decide to join the study, you will need to sign or thumbprint a consent form saying you agree to be in the study. You will receive a copy of the consent form.

Why is this study being done?

The study is conducted to determine the pattern and factors influencing self-medication among caregivers of under-five children in the Central River Region.

The purpose of the study is to gain new knowledge on circumstances surrounding the self-medication of under-five children in rural areas of the Gambia. Previous studies on self-medication of under-five children were mostly conducted in urban areas, prompting the need to also investigate the pattern in rural areas. The findings of the study will inform decisions and policies that will benefit your community and the nation at large.

We will tell the results of this study to your community.

What does this study involve?

This study only involves answering questions about the self-medication of under-five children. The study participants will include caregivers of under-five children who show symptoms of any febrile illnesses 4 weeks prior to the study. A questionnaire will be used to conduct the interview in not more than 30 minutes.

If the research study needs to be stopped for any reason, we will let you know.

What harm or discomfort can you expect in the study?

This study does not involve any procedure that will bring harm or discomfort to you.

What benefits can you expect from the study?

This study will contribute to the knowledge of self-medication in the Gambia. It will also guide healthcare providers and policymakers to come up with community interventions that will address or improve on the factors responsible for the practice of self-medication.

Will you be compensated for participating in the study?

You will not get paid for the study. However, your participation will contribute immensely to the findings that will be gathered during the study, which will benefit your community and the entire nation.

What happens if you refuse to participate in the study or change your mind later?

You are free to join the study or not and you are free to stop being in the study any time without giving a reason. If you do not want to continue with the study, we will use only the information already collected from you. If we find new information during the study that may change if you can still be in the study, we will inform you as soon as possible.

How will personal records remain confidential and who will have access to it?

All information that is collected about you in the study will be kept strictly confidential. Your personal information will only be seen by the study team members, the sponsor, and if necessary, the Ethics Committee and Government authorities.

Who should you contact if you have questions?

If you have any questions or are worried you can call Mrs [[Haita Ndimballan](#)] on [+220 3434325]

Please feel free to ask any questions you might have about the study.

Who has reviewed this study?

This study has been checked by scientists at the Medical Research Council and by the Gambia Government/MRC Joint Ethics Committee. The Ethics Committee protects your rights and well-being and has given permission for it to take place.

obtaining consent

**I attest that I have explained the study information accurately in _____
and was understood to the best of my knowledge by the participant. The participant has freely
given consent to participate *in the presence of the above-named witness (where applicable).**

Signature of person
obtaining consent

Date (dd/mmm/yyyy) Time (24hr)

* Only required if the participant is unable to read or write.

Appendix II

Quantitative Questionnaires

Study title: Caregivers' self-medication practices for perceived febrile illnesses among under-five children in the Central River Region, the Gambia

Definitions

Self-medication

Self-medication has traditionally been defined as the taking of drugs, herbs, or home remedies on one's own initiative, or on the advice of another person, without consulting a doctor.

Febrile illness

It is the increase in body temperature in response to infectious diseases caused by bacteria, viruses, parasites, or fungal infections.

The questionnaire will be administered in the languages that the respondents understand better.

This tool was administered to the respondents following written informed consent.

SECTION A: Sociodemographic characteristics of respondents

1. Age of respondent in years (Age as of last birthday)

.....

2. Gender of respondent

i. Male

ii. Female

3. Age of child (In months)

.....

4. Gender of child

i. Male

ii. Female

5. District

i. Fulladu west

- ii. Niamina East
- iii. Niani

6. Level of education

- i. No formal Education
- ii. Primary
- iii. Secondary
- iv. Tertiary

7. Marital status

- i. Single
- ii. Currently married/Living with a partner
- iii. Divorced
- iv. Widowed
- v. Separated

8. Ethnicity

- i. Mandinka
- ii. Wolof
- iii. Fula
- iv. Jola
- v. Others (specify).....

9. Work status

- i. Employed
- ii. Not employed

10. Occupation

- i. Civil servant
- ii. Business
- iii. Farming
- iv. Student
- v. Housewife/ Stay-at-home parent
- vi. Others (specify).....

11. Caregiver income per month (in Dalasi)

.....

12. Relationship of caregiver with child

- i. Mother
- ii. Father
- iii. Guardian

SECTION B: Knowledge of caregivers on childhood febrile illnesses

13. Where do you usually obtain information on childhood illnesses?

- i. Television Yes No
- ii. Radio Yes No
- iii. Newspaper Yes No
- iv. Health talks during immunization clinics Yes No
- v. Family members Yes No
- vi. Neighbours Yes No
- vii. Friends Yes No
- viii. Pharmacist Yes No
- ix. Doctor Yes No
- x. Traditional healer/marabout Yes No
- xi. Social media Yes No
- xii. Google/Internet search Yes No
- xiii. Community/Online groups of parents Yes No
- xiv. Others (specify).....

14. What are some of the common childhood febrile illnesses?

- i. Fresh cold/Upper respiratory tract infection Yes No
- ii. Chest infection/Pneumonia Yes No
- iii. Measles Yes No
- iv. Gastroenteritis Yes No
- v. Malaria Yes No
- vi. Skin infection Yes No
- vii. Eye infection Yes No
- viii. Nappy rash Yes No
- ix. Injury/trauma Yes No
- x. Others (specify).....

15. What are the main causes of childhood febrile illnesses?

- i. Germs Yes No
- ii. Bacteria Yes No
- iii. viruses Yes No
- iv. Witches Yes No
- v. Evil spirits Yes No
- vi. Others (specify).....

16. How can you tell when a child is ill?

- i. Increase in body temperature Yes No
- ii. Change in behavior Yes No
- iii. Crying too much Yes No
- iv. Others (specify).....

17. Fever can be transmitted from one child to another

- i. True
- ii. False

18. Antibiotics are necessary in the treatment of fever

- i. True
- ii. False

19. All febrile illnesses should be treated with antibiotics

- i. True
- ii. False

20. When should a caregiver seek medical attention for a child sick with a febrile illness?

- i. Immediately symptoms begin Yes No
- ii. When symptoms become worse Yes No
- iii. When there are no medications at home Yes No
- iv. Others (specify).....

21. What actions should a caregiver take when a child is sick with a febrile illness?

- i. Visit a health facility Yes No
- ii. Visit a pharmacy/drug store Yes No
- iii. Treat the child at home Yes No
- iv. Visit a traditional healer Yes No
- v. Others (specify)

22. How can childhood febrile illnesses be prevented?

- i. Vaccination Yes No
- ii. Good hygiene Yes No
- iii. Healthy and balanced diet Yes No
- iv. Using preventive measures (e.g. bed nets, chemoprophylaxis) Yes No
- v. Others (specify).....

SECTION C: Caregiver’s Experience of the most recent febrile illness the child had in the last four weeks

23. Name the signs/symptoms of your child's most recent febrile illnesses during the past four weeks

- i. Fever Yes No
- ii. Cough/runny nose Yes No
- iii. Diarrhoea Yes No
- iv. Difficulty in breathing Yes No
- v. Vomiting Yes No
- vi. Rashes Yes No
- vii. Weakness Yes No
- viii. Others (specify).....

24. Were you able to determine the illness your child suffered from?

- Yes
- No

25. What illness did you suspect when the mentioned symptoms started?

- i. Fresh cold/Upper respiratory tract infection
- ii. Chest infection/Pneumonia
- iii. Measles
- iv. Gastroenteritis
- v. Malaria
- vi. Skin infection
- vii. Eye infection
- viii. Nappy rash
- ix. Injury/trauma
- x. Others (specify).....

26. What was the first action you took to treat the illness mentioned in Q25?

- i. Visit a health facility where the child was treated
- ii. Visit a traditional healer/marabout
- iii. Visit a health care provider at home
- iv. Self-medicate with drugs bought from pharmacy
- v. Gave the child leftover drugs from previous illness
- vi. Others (specify).....

If options (i, ii, and iii) are selected, end the interview.

SECTION D: Self-medication practices for the perceived febrile illness the child had in the last 4 weeks

27. What medication/s did you administer to your child when the signs/symptoms in Q23 started?

- i. Paracetamol/Ibuprofen Yes No
- ii. Cough syrup Yes No
- iii. Antibiotics Yes No
- iv. Antimalarial drugs Yes No
- v. Oral rehydration solution Yes No
- vi. Teething syrups Yes No
- vii. Traditional/Herbal remedies Yes No
- viii. Others (specify).....

28. Can I see the medication/s you administered?

- i. Yes
- ii. No
- iii. Not available

If medication/s are sighted, provide the name/s.....

29. Where did you obtain the medication/s from?

- i. Pharmacy Yes No
- ii. Drug hawkers Yes No
- iii. Family members Yes No
- iv. Neighbours Yes No
- v. Friends Yes No

- vi. Leftover drugs Yes No
- vii. Traditional healer/marabou Yes No
- viii. Others (specify).....

30. For which of the signs/symptoms mentioned in Q23 did you self-medicate your child most?

- i. Fever Yes No
- ii. Cough/runny nose Yes No
- iii. Diarrhoea Yes No
- iv. Vomiting Yes No
- v. Rash Yes No
- vi. Difficulty in breathing Yes No
- vii. Others (specify).....

31. How do you normally determine the appropriate dosage of medication for your child?

- i. Reading the label instructions
- ii. Asking a pharmacist
- iii. Asking a family member, friend, or neighbour
- iv. Consulting a healthcare professional
- v. Guess the dosage based on previous use
- vi. Others (specify).....

32. For how long did the illness last? (in days)

.....

33. What was the outcome of the illness with self-medication?

- i. Child got well with self-medication
- ii. Illness became worse, tried another medication
- iii. Illness became worse, took child to pharmacy
- iv. Illness became worse, took child to health facility (health center, private hospital, clinic)
- v. Others (Specify).....

SECTION E: Factors influencing self-medication for the febrile illness

34. What led you to self-medicate your child when he/she had the febrile illness in the last 4 weeks?

- | | | | |
|-------|---------------------------------------|------------------------------|-----------------------------|
| i. | Financial constraints | Yes <input type="checkbox"/> | No <input type="checkbox"/> |
| ii. | Far distance to the health facility | Yes <input type="checkbox"/> | No <input type="checkbox"/> |
| iii. | Minor illness of child | Yes <input type="checkbox"/> | No <input type="checkbox"/> |
| iv. | Bad attitude of health care workers | Yes <input type="checkbox"/> | No <input type="checkbox"/> |
| v. | Knowledge of the symptoms | Yes <input type="checkbox"/> | No <input type="checkbox"/> |
| vi. | Long waiting hours at health facility | Yes <input type="checkbox"/> | No <input type="checkbox"/> |
| vii. | Experience in self-medication | Yes <input type="checkbox"/> | No <input type="checkbox"/> |
| viii. | Availability of leftover drugs | Yes <input type="checkbox"/> | No <input type="checkbox"/> |
| ix. | Mistrust in the health system | Yes <input type="checkbox"/> | No <input type="checkbox"/> |
| x. | Others (specify)..... | | |

35. How far away is the place you got the medication/s from your place of residence? (In meters)

.....

36. How far is the nearest hospital/health facility from your place of residence? (In meters)

.....

37. What is your usual source of information on self-medication?

- | | | | |
|-------|-----------------------------|------------------------------|-----------------------------|
| i. | Television | Yes <input type="checkbox"/> | No <input type="checkbox"/> |
| ii. | Radio | Yes <input type="checkbox"/> | No <input type="checkbox"/> |
| iii. | Newspaper | Yes <input type="checkbox"/> | No <input type="checkbox"/> |
| iv. | Family members | Yes <input type="checkbox"/> | No <input type="checkbox"/> |
| v. | Neighbours | Yes <input type="checkbox"/> | No <input type="checkbox"/> |
| vi. | Friends | Yes <input type="checkbox"/> | No <input type="checkbox"/> |
| vii. | Pharmacist | Yes <input type="checkbox"/> | No <input type="checkbox"/> |
| viii. | Doctor | Yes <input type="checkbox"/> | No <input type="checkbox"/> |
| ix. | Traditional healer/marabout | Yes <input type="checkbox"/> | No <input type="checkbox"/> |
| x. | Leaflet in the pack of drug | Yes <input type="checkbox"/> | No <input type="checkbox"/> |

- xi. Social media Yes No
- xii. Google/Internet search Yes No
- xiii. Community/online groups of parents Yes No
- xiv. Others (specify).....

38. How confident are you in the accuracy of the information you find from these sources when it comes to self-medicating your child?

Sources of self-medication information	Very confident	Somehow confident	Confident	Not confident at all
Television	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Radio	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Newspaper	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Family members	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Neighbours	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Friends	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Pharmacist	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Doctor	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Traditional healer/marabout	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Social media	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Leaflet in the pack of drug	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Google/Internet search	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Community/online groups of parents	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Others.....	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Appendix III

Qualitative questionnaires

a. Focus Group Discussions

Study title: Caregivers' self-medication practices for perceived febrile illnesses among under-five Children in the Central River Region, the Gambia

Introduction

Thank you for participating in this study aimed at understanding the reasons, behaviors, and perceptions surrounding self-medication. Your insights will contribute to a better understanding of self-medication practice. Please take a moment to answer the following questions thoughtfully and honestly.

This tool was administered to the respondents following written informed consent. It was administered in local languages that the respondents understand better.

Respondents: Caregivers of under-five children who have practiced self-medication

Participants' information

#	Age	Sex
1.		
2.		
3.		
4.		
5.		
6.		
7.		
8.		

Name of community:

Definitions

Self-medication

Self-medication has traditionally been defined as the taking of drugs, herbs, or home remedies on one's own initiative, or on the advice of another person, without consulting a doctor.

Febrile illness

It is the increase in body temperature in response to infectious diseases caused by bacteria, viruses, parasites, or fungal infections.

Reasons for self-medication for the febrile illnesses

Questions

Q1: Do you know the signs/symptoms that under-five children often present in your village? If yes, please briefly describe them.

Q2: How do caregivers of under-five children identify an illness when a child starts presenting signs/symptoms?

Q3: Can you explain how caregivers of under-five children respond to childhood febrile illnesses in your community? Please give your experiences. Are there local ways of treating common illnesses among children? Please elaborate more on how it is carried out.

Q4: Can you explain how you normally obtain information on self-medication? What sources do you rely on most?

Q5: Can you explain how people normally decide on when to self-medicate a child?

Q6: Explain the reasons that influence the self-medication of under-five children in your village.

Q7: What is your knowledge about the negative effects of self-medication?

Q8: Have you ever experienced potential risks associated with self-medication, such as misdiagnosis, drug interactions, or overuse of antibiotics? If yes, what was your experience?

b. In-Depth Interviews

Study title: Caregivers' self-medication practices for perceived febrile illnesses among under-five Children in the central river region, the Gambia

This tool was administered to the respondents after a written informed consent. It was administered in local languages that the respondents understood better.

Introduction

Thank you for participating in this study aimed at understanding the reasons, behaviors, and perceptions surrounding self-medication. Your insights will contribute to a better understanding of self-medication practice. Please answer the following questions thoughtfully and honestly.

Participant information

Age:

Sex: Male Female

Name of community:

Respondents: Caregivers of under-five children who practiced self-medication.

Definitions

Self-medication

Self-medication has traditionally been defined as the taking of drugs, herbs, or home remedies on one's own initiative, or on the advice of another person, without consulting a doctor.

Febrile illness

It is the increase in body temperature in response to infectious diseases caused by bacteria, viruses, parasites, or fungal infections.

Reasons for self-medication for febrile illnesses

Questions

Q1: Can you remember the illnesses your child suffered from during the past four weeks? If yes, describe the most recent one?

Q2: Were you able to identify the illness your child suffered from? If yes, can you explain how you were able to identify the illness?

Q3: How did you respond when the illness started? Describe the actions you took.

Q4: Describe the medications you administered. Give details of the medication types and their local names if possible.

Q5: Can you explain how you treated the illness?

Q6: How often did you administer the drugs to your child when he/she fell ill? Give a breakdown of how many times a day or a week.

Q7: Where did you obtain the medications from? Provide all sources.

Q8: How did you obtain advice to self-medicate your child?

Q9: Explain the reasons that motivated you to self-medicate your child?

Q10: What is your knowledge about the negative effects of self-medication?

Q11: Have you ever experienced potential risks associated with self-medication, such as misdiagnosis, drug interactions, or overuse of antibiotics? If yes, what was your experience?

Appendix IV

Work Plan

ACTIVITY	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D
Proposal development											
Submission for ethical clearance											
Questionnaire development											
Pretesting											
Data collection											
Data analysis and writing the findings											
Dissertation report writing											
Final submission of research project											

Appendix V

Ethical approval

The Gambia Government/MRC Joint
ETHICS COMMITTEE

C/o MRC Unit: The Gambia @ LSHTM, Fajara
P.O. Box 273, Banjul
The Gambia, West Africa
Fax: +220 – 4495919 or 4496513
Tel: +220 – 4495442-6 Ext. 2308
Email: ethics@mrc.gm

Mrs Haia Ndimballeh
University of Ibadan
23 October 2023

Dear Mrs Ndimballeh

Study Title: Caregivers' self-medication practices for perceived febrile illnesses among under five children in Central River region, The Gambia

Project ID/ethics ref: 29505

Thank you for responding to the issues raised by the Gambia Government/MRCG Joint Ethics Committee at its meeting held on 31 August 2023.

Confirmation of ethical opinion

On behalf of the Committee, I am pleased to confirm a favourable ethical opinion for the above research on the basis described in the application form, protocol and supporting documentation.

Approved documents

The final list of documents reviewed and approved by the Committee is as follows:

Document Type	File Name	Date	Version
Investigator CV	CV Haia	15/05/2023	1.0
Covering Letter	Cover Letter_Request for clarification - 3	21/09/2023	3.0
Information Sheet	information sheets and informed consent_3	21/09/2023	3.0
Protocol / Proposal	Revised Questionnaire	27/09/2023	3.0
Protocol / Proposal	PROTOCOL	27/09/2023	3.0

After ethical review

The Principal Investigator (PI) or delegate is responsible for informing the Ethics Committee of any subsequent changes to the application. These must be submitted to the Committee for review using an Amendment Form. Amendments must not be initiated before receipt of written favourable opinion from the Committee.

The PI or delegate is also required to notify the Ethics Committee of any protocol violations and/or Suspected Unexpected Serious Adverse Reactions (SUSARs) which occur during the project by submitting a Serious Adverse Event form. An annual report should be submitted to the Committee using an Annual Report Form on the anniversary of the approval of the study during the lifetime of the study. At the end of the study, the PI or delegate must notify the Committee using an End of Study Form.

All aforementioned forms are available on the ethics online applications website and can only be submitted to the committee via the website at: <http://leo.lshtm.ac.uk>. Additional information is available at: www.lshtm.ac.uk/ethics.

With best wishes

Yours sincerely

Dr Mohammadou Kabir Cham

Chairperson, Gambia Government/MRCG Joint Ethics Committee

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